

Review

Sweet tailoring of glyco-modulatory extracellular matrix-inspired biomaterials to target neuroinflammation

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SUMMARY

Neuroinflammation is a highly reactive response that has not been addressed due to its complexity. Some of its molecular pathways, such as glycosylation, have been neglected in the past. Despite the intricacy and diversity of the glycome, there has been an increased interest in this field of study, which has resulted in fostering advances in glycobiology and glycochemistry. These advances have supported the emergence of a new class of glyco-engineered approaches, in which biomaterial-based strategies can address different disease glycophenotypes. Even though these are not extensively used yet, this review aims to provide a resourceful toolbox to build a wide variety of novel materials that can be designed to tackle the glyco-dysregulations seen in neuroinflammation. By assembling the already-well-described knowledge from glycobiology and chemistry, the best of both worlds can be harnessed toward the emergence of a new biomaterial science branch of study: polymeric-based glyco-modulatory materials.

INTRODUCTION

Neuroinflammation is the general term used to describe inflammatory cascades centralized in the central nervous system (CNS) and/or peripheral nervous system (PNS).¹ This phenomenon encompasses both the nervous and the immune systems, hence the complexity and challenge for resolution. In the case of the CNS, neuroinflammation usually arises from traumatic or pathological injuries to the brain or spinal cord. The prevalence of CNS-related brain and spinal cord injuries was ~55 million and 27 million, respectively, worldwide in the last 5 years, representing serious unsolved health and societal problems.² The biological mechanisms behind neuroinflammation depend on a multitude of features such as the context of disease, type of injury or infections, and duration, all of which determine the immune, biochemical, physical, physiological, and behavioral consequences. Any CNS injury involves an interplay between inflammatory and natural restorative processes whose balance dictates the outcome of the injury, and which depends mainly on microglia, astrocytes, endothelial cells, and infiltrating peripheral immune cells such as macrophages or T cells.¹ It is known that any cellular function and mechanisms are intimately dependent on the secretome. These proteins are usually altered through multiple post-translation modifications, primarily through glycosylation (addition of glycans to the protein backbone, which modulates their structure and functional role).³ In mammalian tissues, glycoproteins are displayed at the cellular and extracellular levels, playing diverse and dynamic functional roles. Thus, glycans are involved in a multitude of cell-cell and cell-extracellular matrix (ECM) interactions that are crucial to maintain any system homeostasis. Changes in cell populations and their

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microenvironment can lead to quick and dramatic changes in the glycans produced and can, therefore, influence and determine the state of a diseased condition due to the highly dynamic, flexible, and variable nature of glycosylation, which does not always rely on genome changes.³ In the past 20 years, glycans have been recognized as significant participants within the CNS, mainly at a functional level such as neural development (where polysialic acid [PSA] is the leading player), neurite outgrowth (primarily influenced by α 2-3 linked sialic acids), synapse formation and stabilization (determined by oligomannosides), neural interactions, and synaptic plasticity (dependent on L-fucose and glycosaminoglycans [GAGs]).⁴

Regenerative approaches that use biomaterial systems that target CNS injuries have been widely investigated within the past decade by tailoring both synthetic and natural polymers. The inherent diversity of the nature of polymeric architecture has permitted the exploration of diverse strategies for multiple modifications on these macromolecules to target neuroinflammation.⁵ ECM-based materials bring the advantage of being naturally present in the physiological milieu, which reduces the risk of rejection or immune reaction to them once implanted/injected, and improves the material integration in the host. In addition, the ECM plays a pivotal role in supporting and promoting cell survival and proliferation, which depends not only on its mechanical and physical properties but also on the biochemical signals it provides. The signaling ability of ECM components is related to the composition of each tissue, which varies across organs, function, and developmental stage. ECM components fulfill different roles through interactions that are mediated by specific motifs on the backbone of the polymer (e.g., peptidic adhesion sequences), on tethered or released factors (e.g., growth factors), and on post-translational modifications that are involved in ECM-ECM and cell-ECM interactions (such as O- and N-glycosylation).³ These natural polymers and their potential blends can serve as valuable components to develop different types of biomaterials, not only to deliver therapeutic molecules but also to display surface-engineered functional moieties targeting a specific molecular feature of the diseased target.

Considering the clinical need to target neuroinflammation and the central role played by glycosylation, functionalizing an ECM-based scaffold with glyco-epitopes or oligosaccharides/polysaccharides that are physiologically relevant in nervous system functions is of interest in developing a new class of bioactive materials. In this review, we lay out comprehensive guidelines to facilitate the design of such novel therapeutics based on ECM polymer backbones that are functionalized with glyco-based moieties that target neuroinflammation. Furthermore, we discuss in detail the different engineering methods that can be used for the synthesis of these biomaterials, as well as the types of systems that will be suitable to be used in the CNS. Finally, we summarize the glyco-engineered strategies that are reported in the literature, which constitute a starting point that offers possibilities to devise our suggested combinations to tackle neuroinflammation.

Rationale for polymer/active biomolecules selection

Relevant ECM-inspired polymer backbones

Because it is the acellular component present in all tissues and organs, the ECM serves as an essential physical scaffolding for the cellular constituents and provides the biochemical and biomechanical cues needed for tissue morphogenesis, differentiation, and homeostasis. The macromolecules constituting the ECM involve polysaccharides, structural proteins, glycoproteins, and GAGs, which, except for hyaluronic acid (HA), also found free in the ECM, are commonly found covalently bonded to proteins in the form of proteoglycans (PGs). Among the categories of

Figure 1. Polymeric building blocks that can be used to construct the next generation of (glyco)-biomaterials that target neuroinflammation
(A) Most relevant ECM-like polymer backbones: hyaluronic acid (i), laminin (ii), fibrin (iii), fibronectin (iv), chondroitin sulfate (v), and collagen (vi).
(B) Significant glyco-modulatory active ingredients: glycan-binding proteins (i), glycoenzymes (ii), polysaccharides (iii), glyco-epitopes/glycomimetics (iv), and glycoenzyme inhibitors (v).

structural proteins and glycoproteins, collagen, fibronectin (FN), and laminin stand out as having both structural, adhesive, and signaling functions. Another important proteinaceous component that has a mechanical and structural role is elastin, providing elasticity in tissues and organs and their interfaces.⁶

PGs can form a hydrated network to fill the extracellular space within the tissue and to interact with other ECM proteins through specific domains and with cell receptors through molecular recognition events. PGs, glycoproteins, and hyaluronan are involved in both physical ECM organization and biomolecular interactions with several cell receptors and with specific binding motifs found on the cell surface and in the ECM. The CNS ECM, in particular, has long been the subject of historical controversy. However, it is now known that PGs occupies >20% of the adult brain volume and contains mainly hyaluronan, chondroitin sulfate (CS), aggrecan, laminin, and tenascin.⁷ The presence of PGs is mainly in the denominated perineuronal net, which surrounds cell bodies and proximal dendrites in a mesh-like structure that interdigitates with synaptic bridges.

In the following sections, selected macromolecular components of the brain ECM and polymeric systems used as ECM mimetics are described (schematic in Figure 1A), to elucidate how these can be used as valuable backbones to engineer natural ECM-inspired biomaterials that can modulate neuroinflammation and other associated processes in pathological conditions occurring in the CNS.

Collagens

Collagens have a role to play during the development of the nervous system, such as in axon guidance and synaptogenesis, terminal differentiation of myelinating Schwann cells, and establishment of the architecture of the brain.⁸ Many collagen-based biomaterial formulations have been proposed and studied to target CNS

pathologies.^{9,10} Because intrinsic collagen-based material performance properties are insufficient due to their differences from native tissues, strategies to improve them by the production of hybrids or cross-linked materials are prevalent and widely implemented. While collagen was previously classified purely as a “structural” protein, it is understood that it is naturally glycosylated with the Glc α 1-2Gal β 1-O disaccharide linked through O-glycosidic linkages to hydroxylysine (Hyl) residues.¹¹ The biological function of this modification is hypothesized to be involved in cell signaling. Glycofunctionalized type I collagen-based materials have been developed and tested, showing the feasibility of obtaining neoglycosylated collagen to target different pathological conditions within the nervous system.^{12,13}

Elastin and elastin-like polymers

Elastin is an essential component of the ECM. The hydrophobic valine-proline-glycine-valine-glycine (VPGVG) pentapeptide is one of the highly repetitive and well-conserved domains of elastin that has inspired the development of elastin-like polypentapeptides or elastin-like polypeptides (ELPs).^{14,15} Because their base monomer is VPGXG (where the guest residue X can be any amino acid except proline), ELPs are versatile in their design, and they undergo distinctive inverse temperature transition.¹⁵ Moreover, the transition temperature (Tt) of ELPs can be tuned by changing the guest residue X, and this tuneability has been harnessed in the field. These customized substrates are referred to as elastin-like recombinamers (ELRs).¹⁶

ELRs bear a variety of side-chain groups available for the conjugation or cross-linking of the polymer backbone. Free amino groups of lysine residues are of interest to anchor new functionalities (e.g., for other click chemistry approaches), to conjugate epitopes of interest, or to perform direct cross-linking. However, residues besides lysines can provide reactive functional groups for further chemical modification or for cross-linking (e.g., carboxylic of glutamic or aspartic acid residues, hydroxyphenylalanines from tyrosines, methyl sulfanyl from methionines, thiol groups from cysteines).¹⁷

Due to their recombinant nature, ELRs have overcome the lack of control over the composition and properties inherent in many natural polymers, granting them excellent compatibility and tuneability. To the best of our knowledge, no information on elastin and tropoelastin glycosylation is available in the literature; however, its expression in brain arterial components together with glycosylated elements and sulfate PGs makes it an exciting polymer to investigate to mimic the general composition of natural ECM.

Fibrin

Fibrinogen is a 340-kDa soluble glycoprotein present in human blood plasma that is essential for hemostasis, inflammation, angiogenesis, and several other biological functions. Naturally formed during blood clotting through the enzymatic lysis of fibrinogen by thrombin, fibrin is a fibrillary polymer involved in hemostasis and wound healing.¹⁸

Physiologically, fibrin is cross-linked by the plasma transglutaminase factor XIIIa, through covalent bonding between glutaminy and lysyl fibrin residues.¹⁹ This natural process has served as inspiration for several fibrin-based biomaterials and drug delivery systems (DDSs), specifically those in the brain.²⁰

Fibrin is usually found glycosylated with complex-type biantennary asparagine-linked glycans (N-glycans). This natural glycosylation presents different degrees of

core fucosylation and distinct types of sialic acids and galactose residues, depending on the species and the tissue from which fibrin is extracted.²¹ The intrinsic glycosylation of fibrin emphasizes the importance of this post-translational modification in the protein backbone, which indicates that it can be enhanced to address a specific target.

FN

FN is a multidomain adhesive glycoprotein ranging from 230 to 270 kDa and is primarily distributed in the ECM. FN is composed of an asymmetric molecule consisting of two subunits linked by disulfide bridges near their carboxy-terminal region. It has been found that FN is covalently cross-linked to collagen types I and III by the action of plasma factor XIIIa.²² A 105-kDa cell-binding domain has been identified in the central region of FN, which contains the sequence arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD). The functional importance of this domain has been evaluated with compounds formed by synthetic peptides that contain the RGD sequence.^{23,24} FN acts as a ligand for a dozen members of the integrin receptor family, promoting cell adhesion and neurite outgrowth from the developing PNS and CNS neurons.²⁴ FN is secreted by glial and endothelial cells to be subsequently assembled into the ECM. It has been reported that FN plays an essential role in extrasynaptic transmission and possesses neuroprotective properties, including an anti-inflammatory effect.²⁵

As for FN glycosylation, this polymer has been reported to have five *N*-glycosylation sites, and the *N*-glycans displayed all are either hybrid or complex, without oligomannose structures present.²⁶ The majority of these *N*-glycans are sialylated and/or fucosylated, which are the glycosylation traits known to play essential roles in the brain. These features can, therefore, be enhanced to target the CNS. Covalently engineered full-length FN-based hydrogels have been synthesized.²⁷ However, even though the mimicking of FN is a valuable strategy in the design of biomaterial, often this glycoprotein is not used as a single component matrix but in combination with other polymer backbones to maximize the final biomaterial performance and efficiency.²⁸

Laminin

Laminins are widely expressed throughout the body and are one of the main components of the basal laminae.²⁹ Their protein structure is made up of three highly glycosylated amino acid chains linked by disulfide bridges. Laminin is synthesized by epithelial cells, muscle, neurons, and bone marrow cells.³⁰ Apart from their structural function, laminins affect cell differentiation and behavior because they are recognized by integrins.³¹ Laminin is also an essential substrate along which nerve axons grow. This property of laminin has attracted considerable attention in the field, and strategies for their incorporation in different biomaterials systems to promote cell adhesion and migration in the neural space have been proposed. Two specific sequences of laminin have been the focus of research, specifically, the laminin peptide domains isoleucine-lysine-valine-alanine-valine (IKVAV) and tyrosine-isoleucine-glycine-serine-arginine (YIGSR), which are involved in neurite extension and cell binding, respectively. Conjugation of these peptide sequences to polymer backbones has been studied for several biomaterial-based therapies targeting the CNS.³² *N*- and *O*-glycosylation of laminins are related to their biological functions and to their ability to interact with other ECM components and with cell receptors, highlighting the importance of these modifications (further reviewed by Marsico et al.³³).

Overall, even though laminin is rarely used as a polymer backbone itself, it has been synergistically combined by efficient conjugation with other ECM-like polymer backbones of interest to generate useful polymeric constructs to target neural disorders.³⁴

HA

HA is an ECM component mainly in skin, joints, and bone, although significant amounts also appear in the lung, kidney, and muscle.³⁵ HA is abundantly present in the brain as well, and it is involved in its healthy development by influencing cell adhesion, migration, axon pathfinding, and regional brain specificity, particularly in the endogenous environment for neural progenitor cells.³⁶ The monomeric unit of HA is a disaccharide made of D-glucuronic acid (GlcA) and N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) linked by alternating β 1-4 and β 1-3 linkages. HA chains can present molecular weights ranging from 8 to 100 million Da, which affects HA structural organization and biological functions.³⁷ HA interacts with other molecules in the physiological milieu through binding sites, which allow it to form complex meshes. In addition, it can exert biological functions through the binding to multiple non-integrin cell surface receptors, such as intracellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1), Toll-like receptors (TLRs) 2 and 4, and CD44, the latter being of particular importance in the CNS context as it is upregulated upon injury.³⁶

The main properties of HA are derived from its structure, which folds in an aqueous solution. At physiological pH, it behaves like a polyanion when it ionizes the carboxylic group of glucuronic acid and acquires the capacity to attract water molecules, creating high osmotic activity, thus making it relevant in the homeostasis of water in tissue.³⁸ Furthermore, HA chains possess the ability to create internal hydrogen bonds in an aqueous medium, resulting in two phenomena: (1) the creation of hydrophobic zones in the chain responsible for the interaction between HA with specific proteins, the cell membrane, and other lipid structures and (2) the stabilization of HA chains in rigid linear helix structures, increasing their viscosity in solution and allowing specific interactions with receptors and enzymes. In turn, this structure allows them to form stable networks from individual molecular weights and concentrations.³⁹ However, these networks can be easily reversed, and therefore non-modified HA intrinsic properties are often not sufficient for biomaterial-based strategies. For this reason, the modification of HA by different cross-linking strategies is usually implemented to stabilize the final construct.⁴⁰

CS proteoglycans (CSPGs)

The family of CSPGs are made up of a protein backbone to which disaccharide repeats called GAGs bind covalently. These disaccharides are made up of GlcA and GalNAc units.⁴¹ The distribution and sulfation pattern of these molecules is critical for the regulation of synaptic plasticity.⁴² Another function of this abundant GAG in the CNS is related to its ability to modulate the activity of neural progenitor cells, influencing their proliferation, maintenance, and differentiation.⁴³ The role of CS proteoglycans in recovery after an injury in the CNS has been a subject of debate; however, it is clear that it plays a crucial role in neural regeneration, and whether it is an obstacle or a facilitator of tissue repair still needs to be fully understood.⁴⁴ Nevertheless, several ECM-based biomaterials that incorporate CS have been reported in the literature.^{45,46} Moreover, further modification of CS through, for example, the attachment of glyco-epitopes of interest or glycan-binding proteins to its structure, can also be of interest to overcome any disadvantages present.

Relevant polymeric components and epitope selection for a glyco-engineered system targeting neuroinflammation

The glycome profiling of CNS disorders and associated neuroinflammation is the first step toward identifying which components can be tackled by using a specifically tailored biomaterial system.⁴⁷ Despite the increased knowledge in this field, glycosylation remains a complex, intricate, and multifaceted process. This depends on a multitude of

factors, such as organelle metabolism, nucleotide availability, and action of distinct glycosylation enzymes (including glycosyltransferases and glycosidases, which add and remove glycan residues, respectively).³ Therefore, tackling glycosylation is not merely a matter of, for example, targeting one enzyme and expecting a specific outcome. This becomes clear when it is known that a specific enzyme can be transiently expressed, having different roles, depending on the disease stage at which it is expressed. The same enzyme can also affect distinct cells differently, and its action will depend on the availability of its substrate as well as on the disease context.

Nevertheless, studies that engage the glycome of various CNS disorders (e.g., spinal cord injury [SCI], traumatic brain injury [TBI], multiple sclerosis [MS], Alzheimer's disease [AD], Parkinson's disease [PD], glioma, or cerebral ischemia) have shown promising results (Table 1). Therefore, it is of interest to investigate the effects of relevant glyco-modulating active ingredients on these pathological conditions.

These therapeutic glyco-based moieties can be broadly divided in glycan-binding proteins, glycomimetics, glycan/saccharide-based residues, glycosylation enzymes, and glycosylation enzyme inhibitors (schematic in Figure 1B), which are discussed thoroughly throughout this section, with a focus on the compounds that have been already tested in the CNS. It is worth noting that neuroinflammation is an underlying molecular mechanism that accompanies all types of CNS injuries (mentioned above), so looking at the glyco-based strategies used to tackle any of these conditions is ultimately correlated with the targeting of neuroinflammation. A comprehensive list of these different (soluble) components tested *in vitro* and *in vivo* in the literature that target glycosylation aspects of the distinct neuroinflammation-related CNS disorders is summarized in Table 1.

Besides showing promising effects as free-circulating molecules, glycan-based structures, or glycomimetics (molecules that mimic carbohydrates while improving their drug-like properties [e.g., enhanced affinity, stability, bioavailability]⁸⁵), can be conjugated to polymeric systems to develop new therapeutic and diagnostic solutions. The development of glycoconjugate polymers has been investigated in the literature, thanks to their added value in mimicking the real multivalent exposition of glycans in the ECM.⁸⁶ The development of glyco-related active components that can modulate neuroinflammation and that have been used so far in CNS diseases^{60,84} provides the first assessment of their potential to be delivered or engrafted through a biomaterial-based approach.

Glycan-binding proteins

Different glycan-binding proteins can recognize distinct sugar residues, and their interaction is commonly followed by the initiation of a cascade of molecular events. These proteins can be broadly classified into antibodies and lectins, and they can act alone or together with canonical ligands to modulate multiple physiological roles. Even though antibodies may be more specific for some glycan epitopes, the use of lectins is overall less expensive, better characterized for their binding specificity, and more stable.³ Since the only glycan-binding proteins used as a potential therapy in the CNS were lectins, this is discussed in the following paragraphs.

In mammals, lectins can be categorized based on their amino acid sequence, structure, and function mainly into C-type of lectins (calcium requiring), S-type lectins (galactins), P-type lectins (Man-6-phosphate binding) and siglecs (I-type lectins).⁸⁷ Although the number of mammalian lectins is finite, they appear to interact in multiple pathways with the surrounding environment, promoting the formation of

Table 1. Selective examples of glyco-based active ingredients that were used in the literature in the context of neuroinflammation in diseased or injured CNS, targeting glycosylation, and resulting in pathophysiological improvement

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
Anti-MAG antibody (Neu5Ac α 2-3Gal β 1-3GalNAc [present in gangliosides in the brain GD1a-, GT1b-endogenous ligands])	glycan/saccharide-based	siglec-4/ myelin-associated glycoprotein	oligodendrocytes and Schwann cells	MS, stroke	siglec-4 is predominantly expressed on the myelin sheath in myelinating cells, where it starts the signaling transduction of inhibitory pathways that contribute to the inhibition of the regenerative ability of the CNS post-injury; this is likely due to the interaction between siglec-4 on oligodendrocytes and the respective neuronal receptors, which mediate signaling between the 2 cell types anti-MAG antibody competitively binds to siglec-4, preventing this interaction and decreasing the inhibitory effect of siglec-4 and protecting the oligodendrocytes from glutamate-mediated oxidative stress-induced cell death	Vyas et al., ⁴⁸ Irving et al. ⁴⁹
CD52 (containing α 2-3 linked SA)	glycan/saccharide-based	siglec-10	predominantly immune cells (e.g., T cells, B cells, macrophages)	MS/neuroinflammation	CD52 binding to siglec-10 and subsequent T cell inhibition requires the DAMP protein, HMGB1; CD52 binds first to the pro-inflammatory box B domain of HMGB1, which promotes the binding of the N-glycan part of CD52 (containing α 2-3 linked SA) to siglec-10; this interaction triggers inhibitory cascades, dampening the neuroinflammation present and restoring immune-inflammatory homeostasis	Bandala-Sanchez et al. ⁵⁰
Siglec-2 (CD22)	glycan-binding protein	CD45	immune cells, mainly B cells	neuroinflammation	siglec-2 is an endogenous ligand for CD45 receptor, abundant on microglia membrane; its prominent role is to negatively regulate microglial activation, leading to an inhibition of LPS-induced TNF- α production; the secretion of siglec-2 by neurons at axon terminals promotes an increased inhibition	Mott et al. ⁵¹

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Table 1. Continued

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
Siglec-11 (expressed on microglia)	glycan-binding protein	polysialic acid	neurons	neuroinflammation	siglec-11 is expressed in microglia and reduces microglial expression of pro-inflammatory mediators (e.g., NOS, IL-1 β) through immunosuppressive signaling, limiting the damage caused by innate immune cells; this is likely due to the ITIM portion of this protein, which antagonizes the phagocytosis-associated ITAM-Syk signaling pathway; siglec-11 binds to PSA residues on NCAM present on neurons, which promote siglec-11 neuroprotective effects; siglec-11 ⁺ microglia also displayed impaired ability to phagocytose apoptotic neuronal fractions, emphasizing its role as a neuroprotective agent and alleviator of microglial neurotoxicity	Wang and Neumann ⁵²
Galectin 1	glycan-binding protein	neuropilin-1 (NRP-1)/plexinA4 receptor complex	neurons	SCI	competitive binding of high abundant (dimeric) galectin-1 to NRP-1/plexinA4 receptor complex in injured neurons interrupts the semaphoring 3A pathway, promoting axonal regeneration and motor recovery post-SCI more specifically, treatment with galectin 1 leads to a decrease in hydrogen peroxide production and promotes re-activation of F-actin cytoskeleton dynamics by endocytosis of plexinA4/galectin 1 complex	Quintá et al., ⁵³ Quintá et al. ⁵⁴
Galectin 1	glycan-binding protein	Core-2-O-glycans low expression of α 2-6 linked sialic acid poly-LacNAc	Th1, T17 cells	MS	galectin 1 selectively eliminates Th1 and Th17 cells (pro-inflammatory phenotype), namely through the binding to increased expression of core-2-O-glycan branched structures and reduced exposure of α 2-6 linked SAs when compared to Th2 cells; this can eventually shift microglia phenotype toward a more regenerative one, increasing the phagocytosis of myelin debris and OPC differentiation	Toscano et al., ⁵⁵ Starosom et al., ⁵⁶ Rinaldi et al. ⁵⁷

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Table 1. Continued

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
<i>Lens culinaris</i> agglutinin (LCA lectin)	glycan-binding protein	A2G2F	whole tissue (mainly glioma cells that overexpress A2G2F)	glioma	glioblastoma tissue display significantly increased expression of A2G2 and A2G2F1; LCA lectin binds specifically to sugar chains with core fucose (including A2G2F); this binding (preferential on glioma cells due to the higher concentration of A2G2F1) induces their apoptosis through morphological alterations and chromatin concentration, inhibiting proliferation in a concentration-dependent manner; it was shown that this cytotoxicity was mediated by caspase-3 cascade	Tsuchiya et al. ⁵⁸
Lactose, Davanat (β1-4 linked D-mannopyranosyl units to which D-galactopyranosyl residues are attached via α1-6 linkage)	glyco-epitopes-based	galectin 1	whole tissue	glioma	Davanat binds to a large area on the surface of galectin 1 that runs across the dimer interface, on the opposite side from where the lactose residues would bind; therefore, the β-galactoside binding domain remains accessible in the galectin 1/Davanat complex for the lactose domains to bind, if needed it has been FDA approved for the treatment of colorectal cancer; however, further research is required to assess its efficacy in the treatment of glioma	Miller et al. ⁵⁹
Lactose, poly-LacNAc	glyco-epitopes-based	galectin 3 inhibitor	microglia	MS/neuroinflammation	galectin 3 is a soluble lectin, released by microglia in inflammatory conditions; it can act as a TLR4 ligand, increasing further the neuroinflammatory cascades; lactose binds competitively to galectin 3, which hinders galectin 3 binding to TLR4, decreasing the pro-inflammatory phenotype	Burguillos et al. ⁶⁰
PST3.1a	glycoenzyme inhibitor	MGAT5 inhibitor	whole tissue, with focus on glioma cells	glioma	PST3.1a inhibits MGAT5, altering the β1-6 GlcNAc N-glycans of glioma-initiating cells and impairing the TGFβR and FAK signaling; this impairs the microtubule and microfilament integrity in the glioma, preventing its invasiveness, proliferation, and migration	Hassani et al. ⁶¹

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Table 1. Continued

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
2-Deoxy-2-3-dehydro-N-acetyl-neuraminic acid (Neu5Ac2en)	glycoenzyme inhibitor	NEU1-NEU4 (sialidases) inhibitor	exosomes produced by microglia	acute stress	microglia can clear polysialic acids through the activity of sialidases, namely when these cells are overstimulated in stressful conditions Neu5Ac2en inhibits sialidases (NEU1–NEU4) activity by competitive inhibition; its administration in an acute stress scenario increased the immobility rate after tail suspension	Abe et al. ⁶²
Thiamet G	glycoenzyme inhibitor	O-GlcNAcase inhibitor	whole tissue	AD, cerebral ischemia, stroke	Thiamet G administration in AD brains increased tau O-GlcNAcylation, impairing the formation of protein aggregates and decreasing neuronal damage Thiamet G administration also improved cerebral ischemia-reperfusion injury and the subsequent motor and neurological damage; the exact mechanism behind this is still being investigated Thiamet G administration was able to shift microglia polarization into an anti-inflammatory phenotype through the inhibition of NF-κB p65 signaling in a rodent model of stroke	Pinho et al., ⁶³ Yuzwa et al., ⁶⁴ Zhu et al., ⁶⁵ Gu et al., ⁶⁶ He et al. ⁶⁷
PDMP	glycoenzyme inhibitor	B4GALT6 inhibitor; glucosyl ceramide synthase inhibitor	whole tissue	MS	LacCer controls astrocyte-promoted neurodegeneration and the recruitment and activation of microglia and CNS-infiltrating monocytes by regulating the production of the chemokine CCL2 and GM-CSF, respectively; since LacCer synthesis depends on the activity of B4GALT6, it can be extrapolated that this regulates astrocyte activation; PDMP inhibits B4GALT6 action, reducing subsequently LacCer synthesis, which blocked local CNS innate immunity and neurodegeneration	Mayo et al. ⁶⁸
Polyman2	glycomimetic	MBL inhibitor	whole tissue	cerebral ischemia/stroke	MBL is overexpressed in ischemic conditions, promoting the complement activation and subsequent immunity cascade; Polyman2 binds to MBL, improving neurological damage and infarct volume, even after 24 h post-ischemia, reducing its toxicity; it is of interest since it has a wide therapeutic window of an application	Orsini et al. ⁶⁹

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Table 1. Continued

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
Polyman9	glycomimetic	MBL inhibitor	whole tissue	TBI	Polyman9 acts preferentially over MBL-C, inhibiting its action, rather than over MBL-A in a dose-dependent manner; therefore, it induces improvement in sensorimotor deficits and neurogenesis; it has specific neuroprotective effects in TBI	De Blasio et al. ⁷⁰
Threonine methyl ester glycosides of disialylT, 3-sialylT, and 6-sialylT (Gal β 1-3(Neu5Ac α 2-6)GalNAc) (monovalent sialoglycans)	glycomimetic	siglec-4/myelin-associated glycoprotein	oligodendrocytes, Schwann cells	MS/neuroinflammation	monovalent sialoglycans promoted axon sprouting proportionally to their MAG-binding affinities; the most potent glycoside was disialylT antigen, followed by 3-sialylT antigen structures, which are usually expressed on O-linked glycoproteins and gangliosides	Vyas et al. ⁷¹
Tegaserod	glycomimetic	HSPG, brain-derived neurotrophic factor, AMPA receptor, NMDA receptor, histone H1 and MARCKS	whole tissue	SCI	tegaserod is a glycomimetic of polysialic acid, and it can promote motor recovery and regrowth of axons when it is administered at the lesion site post-SCI; this corroborates that the functionality of the polysialic acid chains is efficiently mimicked	Pan et al. ⁷²
rhC1-INH	glycoprotein	C1 inhibitor (complement system)/MASP inhibitor	whole tissue	cerebral ischemia/stroke	rhC1-INH can bind MBL in cerebral vessels and reduce cerebral damage even when administered 18 h post-ischemia, presenting a wide therapeutic window for stroke	Gesuele et al. ⁷³
GM1	ganglioside (saccharide unit)	different receptors (e.g., NGF receptor, GDNF receptor, α -synuclein)	whole tissue	PD	GM1 systemically administered can reach the brain and restore tyrosine hydroxylase expression and neurotransmitter abundance, while reducing aggregated nigral α -synuclein levels; this is likely due to the interaction between the oligosaccharide portion of GM1 and specific membrane proteins	Wu et al., ⁷⁴ Chiricozzi et al. ⁷⁵
Heparinase-I	glycosidase (enzyme)	enzymatic degradation of HSPGs	monocytes	neuroinflammation	HSPGs expressed by endothelial cells in the brain play a role in monocyte migration; treatment of these with heparinase-I allowed for the digestion of HS side chains and did not affect cell viability; at the same time, it significantly reduced the transendothelial migration of monocytes	Floris et al. ⁷⁶

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Table 1. Continued

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
ChABC	glycosidase (enzyme)	enzymatic degradation of CSPGs	whole tissue/ECM	SCI	CSPGs inhibit axonal regeneration and OPCs differentiation and migration; treatment with chABC reverses the inhibitory effects of CSPGs on an SCI scenario through the enzymatic digestion of these proteoglycans; this increased the number of OPCs around the lesion site and promoted axonal sprouting	Siebert et al., ⁷⁷ Bradbury et al., ⁷⁸ Kilcoyne et al. ⁷⁹
MGAT3	glycosyltransferase (enzyme)	catalyzes the addition of bisecting GlcNAc (β 1-4 N-acetylglucosamine) to the β -mannose of the trimannosyl core of N-linked glycans	whole tissue	AD	MGAT3 catalyzes the formation of bisecting N-glycans, which was shown to reduce A β production in AD brains, protecting against further neurological damage; the exact mechanism occurring requires further study	Akasaka-Manya et al. ⁸⁰
ST6GAL1	glycosyltransferase (enzyme)	catalyzes the addition of α 2-6 SAs to a β 1-4 linked galactose	whole tissue-focus on glioma cells (α 3 β 1 integrin)	glioma	ST6GAL1 promotes the replacement of α 2-3 SAs for α 2-6-sialic acids; ST6GAL1 hinders cell invasion and spreading; changes in the linkages and expression levels of SA in α 3 β 1 integrin play a role in glioma-ECM interaction	Yamamoto et al. ⁸¹
VCS	glycosidase (enzyme)	hydrolyses terminal N- or O-acyl-neuraminic acids that are α 2-3, α 2-6, or α 2-8 linked to galactose, Hex, Nac, or N- or O-acylated neuraminyl residues in glycoconjugates or colominic acid	whole tissue	PD	VCS administration led to an increase in GM1 levels; this resulted in a significant increase in striatal dopamine levels and nigral dopaminergic neuron survival the results obtained were similar to the ones seen upon the administration of GM1, indicating that enzymatic conversion of polysialogangliosides to GM1 could be an alternative strategy to increase GM1 levels in the brain, as a neuroprotective therapy	Schneider et al. ⁸²
GALNT6	glycosyltransferase (enzyme)	catalyzes the initial reaction in O-linked oligosaccharide biosynthesis, the transfer of an N-acetyl-D-galactosamine residue to a serine or threonine residue on the protein receptor	whole tissue	AD	GALNT6 acted on APP promoting O-glycosylation, and reducing both A β 40 and A β 42 generation; this is potentially due to an altered susceptibility of APP to secretases; further studies are required to determine the specific mechanism	Akasaka-Manya et al. ⁸³

(Continued on next page)

Table 1. Continued

Active ingredient	Type of active ingredient	Target/chemical action	Cellular target	Disease target	Therapeutic action in the diseased context	Ref.
NEU1	glycosidase (enzyme)	hydrolyses polysialic acid chains	neurons	neuroinflammation	polysialic acid in neurons is cleared upon the action of sialidase NEU1 present on the exovesicles secreted from activated microglia post-LPS-stimulus; this clearance is accompanied by the release of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (which is retained by polysialic molecules), promoting axonal sprouting and subsequent neuroprotection	Sumida et al. ⁸⁴

AD, Alzheimer's disease; A β , amyloid beta; AMPA, α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid; APP, amyloid precursor protein; B4GALT, β 1-4-galactosyltransferases; C1-INH, C1 inhibitor; ChABC, chondroitinase ABC; CCL2, chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 2; CD45, protein tyrosine phosphatase, receptor type C, or cluster of differentiation 45; CD52, cluster of differentiation 52; CNS, central nervous system; CSPGs, chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans; DAMP, damage-associated molecular patterns; ECM, extracellular matrix; FDA, US Food and Drug Administration; GALNT, polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase; GDNF, glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor; GM1, monosialotetrahexosylganglioside; GM-CSF, granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor; HMGB1, high-mobility group box 1 protein; HSPGs, heparan sulfate proteoglycans; IL-1 β , interleukin-1 β ; ITIM, immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory motif; ITAM, immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif; LacCer, lactosylceramine; LCA, *Lens culinaris* agglutinin; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; MAG, myelin-associated glycoprotein; MARCKS, myristoylated alanine-rich C kinase substrate; MASP, mannose-binding protein-associated serine protease; MBL, mannose binding lectin; MS, multiple sclerosis; MGAT, α 1-(3/6)-mannosyl-glycoprotein β -N-acetylglucosaminyltransferases; NEU, neuraminidase; NF- κ B, nuclear factor κ B; NGF, nerve growth factor; NMDA, N-methyl-D-aspartate; NOS, nitric oxide species; NRP1, neuropilin-1; OPC, oligodendrocyte progenitor cell; PD, Parkinson's disease; PDMP, D-threo-1-phenyl-2-decanoylamino-3-morpholino-1-propanol; PST3.1a, 3-hydroxy-4,5-bis-benzyloxy-6-benzyloxymethyl-2-phenyl-2-oxo-2 λ 5-[1,2]oxaphosphinane; rh, recombinant human; SA, sialic acid; SCI, spinal cord injury; ST6GAL, β -galactoside β 2-6-sialyltransferase; TBI, traumatic brain injury; TGF β R, transforming growth factor- β receptor; TLR4, Toll-like receptor 4; VCS, *Vibrio cholerae* sialidase.

multiple combinations to tune specificity finely. These recognition systems are the prominent participants in the mediation of multiple physiological processes, such as inflammation and immune responses, cell adhesion, proliferation, migration, cytotoxicity, neuronal signaling transmission, and protein trafficking, among others.⁸⁷

C-type lectins require calcium to bind to their respective glycans and can be broadly divided into two groups, mannose-binding lectins (MBLs; bind to mannose and *N*-GlcNAc) and Gal-type lectins (bind to Gal and *N*-GalNAc), depending on glycan recognition specificity, more specifically on the orientation of the 3- and 4-hydroxyl groups of monosaccharides that interact with the primary ligand-binding site.⁸⁸ C-type lectins contain one or more carbohydrate recognition domains (CRDs), which seem to be overall conserved, whereas the organization and topology of the non-CRD sites are various.⁸⁷ CRDs are present on the surface of multiple cell types and involved in inflammatory processes such as macrophages and microglia. There have been reports of proteins with C-type lectin domains involved in CNS disorders, such as tetranectin (present in myelinated fibers and potentially involved in the modulation of scarring of MS lesions⁸⁹) and C-type lectin-like domain family 16A (CLEC16A; possesses single nucleotide polymorphisms associated with MS and other autoimmune disorders, and was shown to be upregulated in rat astrocytes post-lipopolysaccharide [LPS] injection).⁹⁰

MBL plays a significant role in neuroinflammation since it is a component of innate immunity and holds the function of pathogen/pattern recognition, crucial for the identification of pathogenic microorganisms, acting on the first line of defense of the host.⁹¹ Binding to MBL initiates the lectin pathway of the complement system, triggering an inflammatory cascade, which emphasizes its upregulation in brain disorders. Given MBL immunity-related functions and upregulation in some CNS conditions, its modulation in the context of TBI is of interest, as has been reported using glycomimetics, which is discussed later in this review.

Selectins also belong to the group of C-type lectins and are involved in leukocyte migration in acute and chronic inflammation processes.⁹² Since their prominent roles relate to blood cells, their importance in the CNS becomes relevant only when there is a disruption or permeabilization of the blood-brain barrier (BBB). For instance, it was shown that mouse brain capillary endothelial cells treated *in vitro* with LPS induced the expression of E- and P-selectins, which was not seen with tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) or interferon γ (IFN- γ) stimuli, indicating that selectin expression at the BBB is differently regulated by distinct inflammatory conditions.⁹³ However, selectins can act as receptors for a multitude of ligands, which may be used to functionalize diverse nano-based systems to facilitate the crossing of the BBB.⁹⁴ One example is the use of dendritic polyglycerol sulfate nanocarriers used to deliver paclitaxel for the treatment of glioblastoma.⁹⁵ However, to the best of our knowledge, the administration or use of selectins themselves has not been studied for the treatment of CNS disorders.

S-type lectins, or galectins, are β -galactose-binding lectins that have conserved cysteine residues. These are secreted, and almost all reported 15 mammalian galectins (except galectins 3, 5, and 10) are dimeric or contain 2 carbohydrate-recognition domains in their structure. This structure is generally conserved and is characterized by 2 β sheets oriented differently and composed of β strands.⁸⁷ The β sheets bind preferentially to Gal β 1-4GlcNAc and LacNAc residues present both on cellular surfaces and in the ECM.⁹⁶

Galectins are tissue specific; therefore, in this review, we focused on the main galectins that have been reported in the CNS (galectins 1, 3, 4, 8, and 9),⁹⁷ which are participants in a multitude of biological processes, such as neuroinflammation and neuromodulation. These have been reported to be involved in various CNS disorders, and are likely to play synergistic and complementary roles in the modulation of CNS homeostasis.⁹⁷ For example, MS pathophysiology has been shown to be associated with a dysregulation in galectins 1, 3, 8, and 9,⁹⁸ whereas stroke, TBI, PD, and prion disease were only related to changes in galectin 3.

Galectin 1 is involved in the suppression of microglial activation and in the regulation of both neurogenesis and oligodendrocyte proliferation in the CNS.^{99,100} Thus, its potential to be used as a therapeutic approach in a context in which there is microglial activation and subsequent neuroinflammatory state becomes clear. There are studies in both MS and SCI in which galectin 1 was successfully used. In the case of SCI, galectin 1 was used to target the neuropilin 1/Plexin A4 complex in injured neurons, which downregulates the semaphorin 3A pathway, leading to a decrease in hydrogen peroxide production and an increase in F-actin cytoskeleton dynamics, subsequently enhancing axonal sprouting and motor recovery.^{53,54} In MS, galectin 1 has been used to target T cells, selectively eliminating Th1 and Th17 cells (pro-inflammatory phenotype), because they have preferential binding to core-2 O-linked glycans and cells with a low amount of sialic acids on their surface, which is characteristic of those cells, but not of the Th2 cells. Therefore, galectin 1 promotes the shift in inflammatory phenotype towards a regenerative one.^{55,56}

Galectin 3, however, has a pro-inflammatory role since it promotes microglial and macrophages activation (through TLR4 binding) and regulates oligodendrocyte differentiation, which explains why it is usually upregulated in various CNS disorders, including glioma.^{101–103} On account of its physiological role, targeting/inhibiting galectin 3 is opportune. This has been pursued in the context of MS and neuroinflammation, using the specific glycans that are galectin 3 ligands (i.e., lactose and poly-Lac structures). Through the administration of these sugar residues, they bind competitively to galectin 3, hindering the lectin binding to TLR4 and preventing the triggering of inflammatory cascades.⁶⁰ This was shown *in vitro* but not yet *in vivo* due to the rapid clearance of these short-sized glycan structures and their low stability.⁶⁰ Nonetheless, inhibition of galectin 3 has been studied in non-neurological scenarios,¹⁰⁴ showing promising results.

Finally, galectin 9 has been described to be involved in the modulation of neuroinflammation, being produced by activated astrocytes and promoting microglial activation,¹⁰⁵ relating therefore to MS and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). In the case of MS, it was seen that in human tissue the presence of this lectin was upregulated upon disease, being localized in the nuclei in microglia/macrophages in active MS lesions and in the cytoplasm of microglia/macrophages in inactive lesions.⁹⁸ These spatial distribution changes are related to its altered function, changes in the environment, or enhanced release into the ECM. Increased expression of galectin 9 was also seen in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) of MS patients, which correlated with the number of lesions seen by magnetic resonance imaging.¹⁰⁶ Regarding ALS, it was seen that galectin 9 expression was upregulated in the spinal cord from patients when compared to age-matched controls, probably as a result of neuroinflammation.¹⁰⁷ However, additional studies are necessary to assess the functional role of this galectin in ALS.

Interestingly, galectin 9 is known to bind to T cell immunoglobulin mucin-3 (TIM-3), negatively regulating Th1 cells and suppressing Th1 autoimmunity, which may indicate that it has a role in preventing prolonged inflammation in target tissues.¹⁰⁸

Therefore, it has diversified functions depending on the molecular context and on the cells on which it acts. So far, galectin 9 has not been targeted in the context of CNS disorders.

I-type lectins contain binding domains with homology to the ones in the immunoglobulin superfamily, mainly expressed by cells of the innate and adaptive immune system.¹⁰⁹ The best-characterized subgroup of I-type lectins is the siglec family (sialic acid-binding immunoglobulin-type lectins), composed of sialic acid-recognizing lectins.⁸⁷ Considering the abundance of sialic acids in neuronal membranes in the CNS, mainly on voltage-gated ion channels, influencing neuronal excitability, they are targets of interest in CNS disorders.¹¹⁰

Siglecs are transmembrane proteins in which the extracellular domain is the binding region. In contrast, the intracellular domain can initiate the signaling cascade, the most common being the immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory motif (ITIM) (on siglec-2 and CD33-related siglecs) or the immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif (ITAM).¹⁰⁹ This highlights the role of siglecs in the regulation of stimulatory or inhibitory receptors on immune cells, influencing multiple physiological processes such as neuroinflammation, neurodegeneration, host-pathogen interactions, autoimmune disorders, and cancer, and making them attractive targets for cell-type-specific therapies. Since mammalian cells display a plethora of glycan structures different from the glycocalyx of microbial pathogens, the binding specificity of each siglec allows for the immune cells to discriminate between self and non-self cells/organisms, regulating the immune system responses.¹¹¹ Siglecs reported in the human CNS are mainly siglec-1 (sialoadhesin), siglec-2 (CD22), siglec-3 (CD33), siglec-4 (myelin-associated glycoprotein [MAG]), siglec-7, siglec-10, and siglec-11,¹¹² whereas in murine CNS the most abundant ones are sialoadhesin, CD22, siglec-E, siglec-F and siglec-H.¹¹³

Siglec-1 (or sialoadhesin) has been reported to be involved in MS and in prion disease, being expressed in microglia and macrophages and playing a role in cell-cell interaction,^{96,114} mainly since it does not possess any ITIM or ITAM domain. The absence of siglec-1 in mice decreased the expression of inflammatory cytokines and the axonal degeneration significantly while increasing the animal lifespan.¹¹⁵ This emphasizes the role of siglec-1 in neuroinflammatory processes and suggests that antagonizing its function can be a therapeutic approach in the case of CNS disorders in which BBB integrity is compromised. Preliminary *in vitro* studies have shown that the use of antibodies targeting sialoadhesin in macrophages (SER4 and 1C2P) can upregulate the expression of Treg cells, which has potential ramifications in delaying MS progression.¹¹⁶ Another possibility would be to have specific sialic acid-containing carbohydrates (potentially bound to ECM proteins) in the injured area, which could target siglec-1 action. However, the efficacy of this remains to be tested.

Siglec-2 (or CD22) is more commonly found on B cells acting as a co-receptor of the B cell receptor, and it contains 3 ITIM domains and 1 ITIM-like domain.¹¹³ Therefore, it regulates B cell response in the course of inflammation in a synergistic action with the B cell receptor, and its absence leads to B cell hyperactivation, which can lead to autoimmune conditions.¹¹⁷ However, it has been shown that siglec-2 expressed by neurons causes a reduction in the inflammatory effects triggered by microglia in an *in vitro* co-culture model of neurons and microglia.⁵¹ In this case, siglec-2 at axon terminals binds to the CD45 receptor, which is abundant on the microglial membrane, leading to an inhibition of LPS-induced TNF- α production, suggesting that the

presence of this siglec could be a therapeutic approach to decrease microglial activation. However, siglec-2 was also reported to modify microglial phagocytosis in the aging brain, reducing the clearance of aggregated proteins and cellular debris.¹¹⁸ The inhibition of siglec-2 using an antibody (anti-CD22) was shown to improve microglial function towards its physiological role, enhancing cognitive function in a mice model, which is of interest in an aging brain. Therefore, it was seen that the role of siglec-2 is dynamic, depending on the context and region. Nevertheless, its targeting is promising since it could help decrease neuroinflammatory cascades.

Siglec-4 (or MAG) is mostly found in myelin sheaths (in oligodendrocytes), playing a role in myelin-axon interaction, which allows for the maintenance of long-term axon stability, structure, and cytoarchitecture.⁹⁷ The primary ligands of siglec-4 are glycan structures with the sequence Neu5Ac α 2-3Gal β 1-3GalNAc, which is very abundant on brain gangliosides such as GD1 and GT1b.⁹⁶ Since the presence of siglec-4 inhibits the regenerative capability of the CNS post-injury, namely nerve regeneration, targeting siglec-4 would be an attractive approach for the treatment of MS.¹¹⁹ The gangliosides, as mentioned above, are functional receptors for siglec-4 inhibitory function, which suggests that manipulating gangliosides are likely to promote nerve recovery post-injury. The use of a neuraminidase (*Vibrio cholerae* sialidase [VCS]) was able to reverse the inhibition of neurite outgrowth since it cleaved the outermost sialic acids of the gangliosides, converting them to nonbinding ganglioside GM1.^{48,120} However, one needs to note that gangliosides may also have differential effects on other cells, playing different roles. The specific anti-MAG antibody has also been used to competitively bind to siglec-4 in stroke, preventing its interaction with sialylated ligands and protecting oligodendrocytes from glutamate-mediated oxidative stress-induced cell death.⁴⁹ This emphasizes the importance of targeting this lectin in the context of different CNS disorders.

Siglec-11 is reported to be involved in the inhibition of inflammation and phagocytosis, binding preferentially to polysialic acids (α 2-8 linked sialic acid) and being expressed by microglia, macrophages, and peripheral blood leukocytes.⁹⁷ Siglec-11 is one of the essential microglial inhibitory motifs and interacts with the neuronal glycocalyx, ameliorating microglia-based neurotoxicity.¹²¹ Its primary ligand is the polysialylated neuronal cell adhesion molecule (PSA-NCAM), which is expressed on both neurons and microglia. However, only the neuronal ligand is effective in suppressing the microglial expression of pro-inflammatory mediators (e.g., nitric oxide synthase, interleukin-1 β [IL-1 β]), limiting the damage caused by innate immune cells and impairing the microglial ability to phagocytose apoptotic neuronal fractions.⁵² This emphasizes the role of siglec-11 as a neuroprotective agent and alleviator of microglial neurotoxicity, which highlights its usefulness as an attractive target.

Glycomimetics

As previously mentioned, carbohydrates possess multiple functions that are crucial for a myriad of biological and physiological processes, namely through their expression on the cell surface, acting as receptors for other cells, molecules, and pathogens. The major drawbacks of carbohydrates as therapeutic drugs are their intrinsic properties of low binding affinity and low stability *in vivo*, as well as the complex and expensive large-scale synthesis and purification of native glycan structures.⁸⁵

Understanding the interactions that occur between these and respective bioactive conformation allows for the rational design of glycomimetics. These retain the functionality of their correspondent glycan, plus enhanced activity and stability, as well as a reduced cost of production. The advances in analytical characterization techniques,

synthetic organic chemistry, and computational modeling also contribute to a better and more accurate design of these molecules, broadening this class of therapeutic drugs, which can address some needs in the treatment of CNS disorders.¹²² The most studied class of glycomimetics for CNS application is the one that targets siglec-4 (or MAG), a protein that inhibits axonal regrowth in an injury scenario and was described previously.¹¹⁹ Paulson and colleagues^{71,123} have been focused on this over the last 2 decades, developing multiple glycomimetics of the Neu5Ac α 1-3Gal β 1-3GalNAc sequence, which is typically expressed by gangliosides in the brain such as GD1a and GT1b. The treatment of neuronal cultures with the most potent sequence (threonine methyl ester glycosides of disialylIT, 3-sialylIT, and 6-sialylIT [Gal β 1-3(Neu5Ac α 2-6)GalNAc]) enhanced axonal sprouting, displaying a potential therapeutic effect.⁷¹

Glycomimetic peptides of PSA have also been developed for the treatment of SCI, mainly by Schachner et al.^{72,124,125} over the last 10 years. PSAs are chains composed of up to 200 α 2-8 linked sialic acid residues and are known to be crucial players in the homeostasis of the nervous system, mainly by acting as a receptor for multiple molecules (e.g., heparin sulfate proteoglycans, histone H1, myristoylated alanine-rich C kinase substrate [MARKS], brain-derived neurotrophic factor) enhancing regenerative processes.^{4,72} It was seen in rodent models that the administration of these glycomimetics (tegaserod,⁷² H-NTHTDPYIPID-OH,¹²⁵ or CSSVTAWTTGCG peptidic sequence¹²⁴) successfully promoted functional recovery and increased axonal density at the lesion site, emphasizing their similar action to the polysialic counterpart. Also, it corroborates that it is possible to reduce a long-chain complex glycan to a small synthetic molecule, which allows the structural modeling of these compounds to optimize their functional properties.

Polyman is another type of formulated glycomimetics, which are MBL ligands and play a critical role in the innate immune system. Polyman glycomimetics have been tested in the context of stroke and TBI, conditions with a significant increase in the MBL response. Polyman9, a glycodendrimer that had been shown to interact with dendritic cell-specific intercellular adhesion molecule-3-grabbing non-integrin (DC-SIGN),¹²⁶ was used in a TBI rodent model, showing a significant improvement in the sensor-motor deficits and in neurogenesis, acting preferentially on the MBL-C isoform, rather than on the MBL-A isoform.⁷⁰ Polyman2, however, was used in an ischemic model. This mannosylated dendrimer showed high affinity to MBL, and its therapeutic action improved neurological damage and infarct volume, having a wide therapeutic window of application (even 24 h after the ischemic event).⁶⁹

Even though the field of glycomimetics is being increasingly studied, there is a need to investigate possible glycomimetic therapeutic approaches for neurological diseases.¹²⁷ This area is still open to explore how glycomimetics can be used in other CNS disorders, such as neurodegenerative conditions (e.g., AD, PD, ALS). Although the exact glyco-molecular signature of these conditions is still not fully understood, the knowledge acquired so far provides potential targets for intervention to reduce neuroinflammation while increasing cell proliferation and synaptic plasticity.

Glycosylation enzymes

Glycosylation is a complex and sophisticated non-template-driven process that depends on numerous molecular factors such as sugar-donor availability, organelle physiology, and molecular and cellular conditions, leading to a formation of a vast and complex plethora of glycan structures.³ However, the leading players in this phenomenon are glycosylation enzymes, broadly divided into glycosyltransferases

(if they add a monosaccharide residue to the acceptor substrate) and glycosidases (if they remove a glycan unit from this chain).^{3,33} Examples of glycosyltransferases are *N*-acetylgalactosaminyltransferases, *N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferases, sialyltransferases, galactosyltransferases, and fucosyltransferases, whereas glycosidases are, for instance, sialidases, galactosidases, fucosidases, and mannosidases.

Thus, even though glycosylation is template independent, the information necessary for glycome synthesis is present within the genome. The human genome includes >300 genes encoding for glycosylation enzymes that contribute to this orchestration, as well as other enzymes involved in the modification and remodeling of glycans, such as sulfotransferases, epimerases, transporters, and others.^{3,128} The cellular glycosylation machinery is, therefore, intricate and influenced by various agents that ultimately give rise to distinct glycoproteins, proteoglycans, and glycosphingolipids. However, the expression of these enzymes is both tissue and cell specific, increasing the complexity of the whole process. Consequently, the construction of glycan structures in a particular cell relies not only on the enzymes produced and expressed but also on the way they cooperate in a biosynthetic network to harmonize the glycan symphony in each cell, which results from the specificities of those enzymes and their sequential action.¹²⁹

Despite the challenge in using glycosylation enzymes as a therapy, some studies have highlighted how these enzymes can be used in particular CNS conditions such as SCI, AD, PD, and glioma. The most successful use of enzymes targeting glycan-based structures has been in the case of the enzymatic degradation of proteoglycans. Sulfate proteoglycans (mainly heparin sulfate proteoglycans [HSPGs] and CSPGs) are known to play an inhibitory role in injury conditions, mainly during neuroinflammatory cascades post-SCI. The enzymatic digestion of these proteoglycans through treatment with heparitinase I and chondroitinase ABC (ChABC), respectively, has shown promising results. Heparitinase I degraded heparin sulfate side chains, reducing the migration of monocytes in an *in vitro* model with brain endothelial cells.⁷⁶ In the case of CSPGs, ChABC was used *in vivo* in SCI rodent models where it promoted axonal sprouting and increased the number of oligodendrocyte progenitor cells (OPCs) around the lesion site while reversing the inhibitory effects of CSPGs.^{77,78} Since both of these enzymes are involved only in the degradation of proteoglycans post-injury and not in their biochemical assembling, it is more straightforward to use them as a therapy in an injury scenario. When it comes to the use of glycosyltransferases and glycosidases, the studies performed (described below) assessed their efficacy in the damaged CNS through nucleic acid transfer.

In the case of AD, the focus was given to MGAT3 (β 1-4-mannosyl-glycoprotein 4- β -*N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase). This glycosyltransferase catalyzes the addition of bisecting GlcNAc (β 1-4 N-GlcNAc) to β -linked mannose from the trimannosyl core of *N*-linked glycans.⁸⁰ This enzyme was shown to be upregulated in AD brains, promoting an increase in bisected structures. This was also reported *in vitro* to occur after cell treatment with A β 42 (the main hallmark in AD). In the same study, it was described that cell transfection with the MGAT3 gene led to a significant decrease in the production of both A β 40 and A β 42.⁸⁰ Also, in this context, GALNT6 (polypeptide *N*-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 6) has been used. This enzyme catalyzes the initial reaction in *O*-linked oligosaccharide biosynthesis, the transfer of an *N*-acetyl-D-galactosamine residue to a serine or threonine residue on the protein receptor, and it was shown to act on amyloid precursor protein (APP), promoting its *O*-glycosylation and reducing both A β 40 and A β 42 production.⁸³

Another enzyme involved in *N*-glycosylation whose potential therapeutic effect was assessed was ST6GAL1 (ST6 β -galactoside α 2-6-sialyltransferase 1). This glycosyltransferase catalyzes the addition of α 2-6 sialic acids to a β 1-4 linked galactose. In the case of cancer, more particularly glioma, it is of interest since glioma cells have been associated with a lower presence of α 2-6 linked sialic acids and upregulated expression of α 2-3 linked sialic acids on their surface. In this case, the cells were transfected with ST6GAL1 to replace the α 2-3 linked with the α 2-6 linked sialic acids. When these cells were transplanted *in vivo*, they did not elicit any tumor formation, which indicates that the linkage is crucial to determine a pathological state.¹³⁰

Regarding glycosides and their use as therapies for CNS disorders, two have been reported so far: VCS for PD⁸² and NEU1 for neuroinflammation.⁸⁴ VCS hydrolyses terminal *N*- or *O*-acyl-neuraminic acids that are α 2-3, α 2-6, or α 2-8 linked to galactose, and Hex, NAc, or *N*- or *O*-acylated neuraminyl residues in oligosaccharides in glycoconjugates, as for example the monosialotetrahexosylganglioside (GM1). GM1 has been reported to be downregulated in PD brains, playing a role in the decrease in dopaminergic neurons and subsequent dopamine depletion.⁷⁴ The administration of VCS increased GM1 levels, which resulted in a significant increase in striatal dopamine levels and nigral dopaminergic neuron survival, similar to what was seen upon the administration of GM1.⁸² This indicates that a VCS-based neuroprotective therapy can comprise an alternative strategy to increase GM1 levels in the brain.

NEU1 (sialidase-1) can be involved in both *O*-linked and *N*-linked glycosylation and hydrolyses sialic acid chains (also in PSA). In this study, a cell line was transfected with NEU1, increasing its production. In parallel, it was shown that the exovesicles released from activated microglia contain NEU1 (unstable in its free form), which affects neuronal physiology by cleaving PSA. This is accompanied by the release of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (which is retained by PSA molecules), promoting axonal sprouting and highlighting the potential of this enzyme as a neuroprotective agent.⁸⁴

As can be seen, the use of glycosylation enzymes (or their transcripts) as therapeutic approaches is still in its infancy, due to the multiple concerns associated with their cell-specific broad functions over different molecules. It should be noted that none of these could be grafted to a polymer backbone since their action would require the enzymes to have the chemical freedom to act suitably on their substrates. However, these enzymes can be potentially encapsulated and delivered through a polymer-based vehicle, allowing for their controlled and localized release.

Glycosylation enzyme inhibitors

As previously mentioned, glycosylation enzymes are crucial for the production and assembly of glycan chains, which have multiple functions and are essential mediators of cellular homeostasis. If these enzymes are downregulated in a diseased state, then it is almost intuitive that to tackle those differences it is necessary to administer the enzyme itself or to use gene therapy with a transcript that is specific for that same enzyme. Nonetheless, if the enzymes are upregulated, mainly glycosyltransferases, the adequate approach usually relates to the administration of a specific inhibitor, which will compete for the active site in the enzyme against the designated substrate. These are generally called substrate analogs or glycoside primers and are small molecules that can be taken up by cells.³ Designing new compounds can be complex and arduous since they may be successful *in silico* and *in vitro*, but not in cellular platforms or animal models. For the same reasons mentioned above, care must be taken when considering interference with enzyme activities.

It has been reported that in the case of gliomas, there is an upregulation in MGAT5 (α 1-6-mannosylglycoprotein 6- β -*N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase A) expression, resulting in an increased branching of *N*-glycans, which ultimately leads to enhanced invasiveness.¹³¹ This is, therefore, an attractive target to address to decrease cancer invasivity. A specific inhibitor has been developed and patented—PST3.1 (3-hydroxy-4,5-bis-benzyloxy-6-benzyloxymethyl-2-phenyl-2-oxo-2 λ 5-[1,2]oxaphosphinane),¹³² which is a crystalline aromatic polymorphic form that binds to MGAT5, inhibiting its action of catalyzing the addition of β 1-6 GlcNAc to *N*-glycan structures in glioma-initiating cells. This impairs the microtubule and microfilament formation and integrity, preventing cells from proliferating and migrating, having an antitumor effect.⁶¹

D-threo-1-Phenyl-2-decanoylamino-3-morpholino-1-propanol (PDMP) is another aromatic compound that has been developed for glycoenzyme inhibition, in this case, B4GALT6. B4GALT6 (β 1-4-galactosyltransferase 6) catalyzes the synthesis of lactosylceramide (a glycosphingolipid), known to be upregulated in MS, promoting astrocyte activation and associated microglial recruitment. PDMP was successfully used *in vivo* to suppress B4GALT6 action and subsequent innate immunity in the CNS and neurodegeneration.⁶⁸

Thiamet G (1,2-dideoxy-2'-ethylamino- α -*D*-glucopyranoso-[2,1-d]- Δ 2'-thiazoline) is probably one of the most studied glycosylation inhibitors in the context of brain disorders since it can cross the BBB, namely for the application in AD. This has a thiazoline ring that is protonated at physiological pH, promoting a more favorable electrostatic interaction (having better steric properties) in the active site of *O*-GlcNAcase (OGA).¹³³

OGA is shown to be increased in AD brains, which reduces protein *O*-GlcNAcylation since it hydrolyzes *O*-GlcNAc residues from proteins, which is particularly important in the case of tau protein.⁶³ Lack of *O*-GlcNAc modification of tau was shown to promote its aggregation and consequent neurotoxicity, leading to an increase in neurodegeneration.⁶⁴ Use of Thiamet G to diminish OGA activity and therefore increase *O*-GlcNAcylation was shown *in vivo* to stabilize tau against aggregation, impairing its misfolding.^{63–65} Thiamet G was also used in other contexts, such as cerebral ischemia⁶⁶ and stroke,⁶⁷ where it was shown to improve motor and neurological damage, and to promote microglia polarization into an M2 phenotype by inhibiting nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) p65 signaling, respectively. Thus, besides increasing protein stability in AD, it also acts as an anti-inflammatory drug in stroke. However, the exact underlying mechanisms of action through which it can improve cerebral ischemia-reperfusion injury and ameliorate stroke events still require further research.

Substrate analogs have also been used in the CNS, particularly Neu5Ac2en (2-deoxy-2-3-dehydro-*N*-acetyl-neuraminic acid [DANA]) in an *in vivo* model of acute stress.⁶² It was able to inhibit the action of sialidases (NEU1–NEU4) through competitive inhibition, preventing the clearance of PSA in neurons and promoting GABAergic neuron functionality. Notably, this phenomenon seems to be region specific and highly dynamic, depending on both the environment and the genome, which poses some hurdles in the development of a therapy, primarily when it is delivered systemically as in this case (intraperitoneal injection). It is worth noting that due to the nature of their action, glycosylation enzymes inhibitors cannot be covalently attached to a backbone either, since they are needed in their unmodified form to block the activity of the enzyme. Thus, they need to be delivered by rather than grafted into a biomaterial platform.

Glycoconjugates

Glycans comprise the most abundant class of molecules in nature, being ubiquitously expressed in all cell surfaces (forming a glycocalyx) and in the matrix surrounding them. They are crucial regulators of cell and tissue fate in the CNS, mainly in a diseased condition. The use of naturally occurring monosaccharides or di-/trisaccharide chains per se as a therapy has been shown to pose some challenging limitations in terms of affinity, selectivity, and *in vivo* targeting. However, the use of natural or synthetic glycoconjugates can represent a solution of interest to address a plethora of clinical needs.

A paramount example is the use of ganglioside GM1 for the treatment of PD. In this case, the GM1 oligosaccharide portion likely binds to specific membrane proteins, promoting the reduction in aggregated nigral α -synuclein levels, which leads to an improvement in motor function.^{74,75} An example of glycoprotein used is the recombinant human C1 inhibitor, which acts on the C1 component of the complement system or on the mannose-binding protein-associated serine protease (MASP), inhibiting their functions. rhC1-INH was shown to be useful to bind MBL in cerebral vessels and reduce cerebral damage in a stroke scenario.⁷³

This overview of the glyco-related active ingredients that can modulate neuroinflammation and that have been used in the diseased CNS provides a first assessment of their potential to be delivered through a biomaterial-based approach or to be engrafted to a biomaterial system. Advancements in the fields of glycobiology and glycochemistry will enable understanding of the fundamental biological mechanisms taking place in different injured conditions. This understanding will enable the development of glyco-analytical platforms that will provide a better characterization of therapeutics developed.

Glycoengineering methods

To exert a particular therapeutic effect in the CNS, ECM-like polymers can be programmed to serve as (1) a backbone to covalently bear and expose specific active epitopes/biomolecules or (2) a matrix or vehicle to physically accommodate and subsequently release active biomolecules of interest. Thus, in this section, the most relevant covalent and non-covalent strategies to influence a glyco-modulatory effect through a polymeric intervention will be elucidated.

Covalent formulation strategies: revealing active epitopes

Efficient synthetic routes to provide new functionalized polymers or polymeric systems are of interest for biomaterial scientists. It is of importance to note that the success of a reaction to modify a particular polymer backbone chemically will not depend entirely on the functional groups available on the polymer backbone but also the specific final biomaterial fabrication strategy and the clinical need. In some cases, a low functionalization degree is sufficient to achieve a desired therapeutic effect, meanwhile higher degrees of functionalization can be a crucial prerequisite for some fabrication strategies or physiological targets.

As a general note to this section, as this review is focused on the synthesis of biomaterials, it is vital to avoid potentially toxic by-products in the selected synthetic path. If a reagent with a certain level of toxicity cannot be replaced and, therefore, must be used, then it is imperative to guarantee its complete removal in the purification steps. For example, glutaraldehyde is an efficient reagent that condenses amines via Mannich reactions, among others. However, unreacted glutaraldehyde leads to toxic effects due to the undesired cross-linking of cellular proteins and tissues, requiring purification.

Figure 2. Most relevant and experimentally efficient covalent strategies for most relevant ECM-like polymer backbones at a glance

Depending on the particular proposed biomaterial-based therapeutic intervention, different epitopes and ECM-like polymer backbone couples can be combined, taking advantage of the available chemical toolbox and glycan building blocks library. The depicted strategies encompass step-efficient synthetic routes, which, involving friendly purification steps, can cater glyco-modulatory engineered biomaterials. Polysaccharide in nature or proteinaceous, the epitopes of interest can be chemoselectively anchored in polymeric chains bearing the suitable reactive functional groups to expose them in the physiological milieu covalently.

By performing chemoselective techniques, uniquely reactive functional group couples from glycans and polymers are combined, resulting in a selective covalent bond formation regardless of the presence of an array of other unprotected functionalities.¹³⁴ Chemoselective strategies, with a particular interest in the field of glycoconjugate polymers, have been thoroughly reviewed.¹³⁵ Supported by the full range of well-established conjugation strategies that can be of use, the most experimentally relevant and useful chemical reactions reported to functionalize ECM-like polymer backbones are described in the following sections and are schematically outlined in Figure 2. The chemical reactions in each of the following strategies are described in Figure 3.

Amide formation

In 1971, the carboxyl groups of polysaccharides (including HA) were, for the first time, converted into substituted amides by the activation of the carboxyl group with a water-soluble carbodiimide followed by a nucleophilic reaction of an amino acid methyl ester with the activated carboxyl group.¹³⁶ Amidation in water using carbodiimide chemistry is the most widely used method for functionalization of natural polymers. This method harnesses the reactivity of the terminal carboxylic groups on polymeric backbones and is also used for the functionalization of other ECM-like polymer backbones bearing terminal amino groups such as collagen or elastin-like polymers. Conjugation through carbodiimide chemistry is based in the activation of carboxyl groups that allow direct reaction with primary amines via amide bond formation.¹³⁷

1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) for aqueous conjugation and *N,N'*-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) for organic solvent-based conjugation are the most widely used and readily available carbodiimides. Considering the need for more friendly synthesis routes, and particularly for HA functionalization, EDC stands out because of its miscibility in water.³⁷ Taking a closer look into the chemical reaction involved (Figure 3), EDC reacts with HA carboxylic acid groups

Figure 3. Most experimentally relevant chemical reactions for efficient conjugation of polymer backbones and epitopes of interest
Aqueous buffer, pH 7.0-10.0 Critical Steps: Oxidation of thiolated product, purification procedures.

to form an active *O*-acylisourea intermediate that is easily displaced by nucleophilic attack from primary amino groups in the reaction mixture.¹³⁸ Consequently, the terminal amino group from the epitope of interest forms an amide bond with the original carboxyl group, and an EDC by-product is released as a soluble urea derivative. If the water-unstable intermediate fails to react with the primary amine, the carboxylic group is regenerated due to the *O*-acylisourea ester hydrolysis. Therefore, to stabilize this intermediate and improve amine reactivity and the overall efficiency of the coupling reactions, *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) or its water-soluble analog (sulfo-NHS) is included in the protocol.¹³⁹ In this way, EDC couples NHS to the carboxylic functional group, forming an NHS ester that is significantly more stable than the *O*-acylisourea ester, enhancing efficient conjugation to primary amines, our nucleophile, at physiologic pH and forming stable amide linkages.¹³⁷ Even though NHS and sulfo-NHS esters present more stability than *O*-acylisourea ester, this does not mean that they are not hydrolytically vulnerable; hydrolysis still occurs but at a slower rate. In water, their instability can result in half-lives ranging from minutes to hours, and since hydrolysis is the essential competing side reaction, the water content or active concentration of water of the pH-dependent reaction solution needs to be accounted for.¹³⁷

When choosing this strategy, it is vital to note that EDC action is most effective at pH 3.5–4.5. MES buffer (4-morpholinoethanesulfonic acid) is a suitable carbodiimide reaction buffer, but if the phosphate-buffered solution and neutral pH conditions are required, the entailed lower efficiency can be compensated upfront by an increased addition of EDC. Some alternatives involve the use of organic solvents, but this is not particularly convenient when working with ECM-like polymers and leads to additional steps in the process. Finally, carboxyl/amine free buffers must be used to ensure successful conjugation.

Notably, and within the scope of this review, considering HA functionalization (or cross-linking) using carbodiimide chemistry, it is vital to keep in mind that HA chains are hydrolyzable. Hence, this polymer can be degraded in physiological media, both in basic and acidic conditions.¹⁴⁰ Although degradation in basic conditions is more significant and faster than in acidic media, there is a compromise that should be achieved between the reaction time for functionalization and the simultaneous HA backbone degradation rate in the presence of MES buffer or similar. In neuroinflammation, the molecular weight of HA biodegradation products released plays a crucial role in the ultimate therapeutic effect.

An alternative to EDC and DCC involves the utilization of 4-(4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazine-2-yl)-4-methylmorpholinium (DMTMM) as a carboxylic group activator. Initially developed for peptide synthesis, DMTMM does not display degradation in the water at room temperature, with 100% recovery after 3 h, overcoming the drawback of EDC, which exhibits a half-life of 3.9 h in water at pH 5.0.

Polysaccharide carboxyl group activation with DMTMM to facilitate the conjugation has been studied and reported.¹⁴¹ In particular, HA amidation assisted by DMTMM takes place through an aromatic substitution, forming an intermediate *s*-triazine ester of HA reactive toward amines, and this reaction has been reported to work both in basic and acidic pH conditions.¹⁴² As previously mentioned, the need for precise pH control is one of the challenges presented by the EDC/NHS conjugation route. Choosing DMTMM as a carboxylic acid functional group activator offers the possibility of working without full pH control. In this regard, to verify the efficacy of DMTMM-mediated amidation with minimal handling, D'Este et al.¹⁴³ reported

HA conjugation to 6 different ligands of interest, setting a starting reaction with pH 6.5, avoiding the use of any buffer, and taking advantage of the proposed self-buffer behavior of HA solutions. The elimination of DMTMM after the reaction was also confirmed. Finally, it is worth noting that some amines may cross-react with DMTMM, impeding further functionalization.

Reductive amination, oxime, N-methoxamine, and hydrazone ligations

The amidation reaction described is useful when a polysaccharide can be functionalized without control of the exposition of particular oligosaccharide or polysaccharide fragments involved in biomolecular recognition processes. The use of glycans as signaling molecules involve the need for differential conjugation strategies to control the biological activities of the motifs used. Glycans containing a free reducing end can be conjugated to proteins or polymer amino groups via reductive amination, oxime, methoxamine, and hydrazone formation.¹⁴⁴ Chemically speaking, the oligo- or polysaccharide reducing end exists as an equilibrium mixture between the cyclic hemiacetal form and the open-chain aldehyde form. The second, being a carbonyl compound, can react with an amine through condensation to afford an imine or iminium ion that is reduced *in situ* or subsequently to form an amine product. In the case of collagen and other proteins, this chemical reaction can be performed in aqueous media. When considering the use of reductive amination to yield polymeric biomaterials exposing specific glycans of interest, it is of the utmost importance to bear in mind that this procedure results in the ring opening of the reducing end monosaccharide. For instance, reductive amination between collagen terminal amino groups and the reducing end of several oligo- or polysaccharides has been reported as a feasible synthetic route to fabricate neoglycosylated collagen-based materials.^{13,145} Although reductive amination has been successfully used in the past to couple glycans to proteins, it has not been without inherent challenges, and the most relevant ones are as follows:

The reducing agent must be stable in water, unreactive with aldehydes and at the same time reactive with iminium ions.

Sodium cyanoborohydride is used exclusively to comply with the requirements above, and, being a toxic reagent, it must be eliminated in the purification steps.

The actual aldehyde form concentration should be low since the lactol/aldehyde equilibrium form of glycans mentioned above is shifted toward the lactol.

Conducting the reaction in water can compromise the formation of the iminium ion due to the unfavored release of a water molecule.

Because of this, the use of an excessive amount of glycans, high concentrations, and extended reactions times are required to overcome all of the previous issues, and hence reductive amination remains a good strategy for the efficiency of the process when the polysaccharide of interest is available in large quantities.¹² Another issue related to this method is the loss of the first unit of the glycan in the conjugation step. This method is therefore useful with di-, oligo-, and polysaccharides, when the first sugar unit can be sacrificed. Along with the previously detailed efficiency issues, in the endeavor to covalently attach a saccharidic cue to collagen through reductive amination, the cyclic structure of the sugar linked to the biomaterial is lost. To overcome this limitation, a strategy allowing for chemoselective conjugation to *N*-methoxyamino-functionalized collagen of an unprotected glycan in aqueous media maintaining its cyclic structure has been proposed.¹⁴⁶ In this work, *N*-methoxyamine-modified collagen films were established using a chemoselective protocol that uses glucose and maltose as a proof of concept.

As mentioned in the introduction of this section, aldehydes react with oxyamino groups to yield oximes. In this way, several oxime-linked neoglycopeptides were obtained. Using an *N*-methoxyamino group, it is possible to maintain, after condensation with unprotected oligosaccharides of interest, the cyclic pyranose form of the first attached sugar in the synthesized neoglycosylated protein.¹⁴⁷ In addition, hydrazone formation is an affordable, well-exploited method to obtain polymer-glycan conjugates from the aldehyde of the selected glycan and a hydrazine group inserted on the polymer chain or linkers.¹⁴⁸ With the reported procedure, polymer backbones can be used, taking advantage of functional groups that are available on the backbone (i.e., amino groups of lysines directly usable in reductive amination) or of functional groups introduced by the direct modification of backbone functional groups or the introduction of linkers (i.e., hydrazide-, aminoxy-, and methoxamine-bearing linkers). In summary, the selected strategy needs to take into consideration all of the actors: the backbone polymer, the glycan residues, and final application of the glycosylated polymer.

Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition

In their milestone publication from 2001, Kolb et al.¹⁴⁹ introduced the concept of “click chemistry,” aiming to encompass a set of robust, selective, and modular “blocks” that can be versatile and efficient enough to work in both small and large scale. For this, the reactions must be broad in scope, simple, high yielding, use mild solvents (preferably water), generate harmless by-products, involve non-chromatographic purification methods, and be stereospecific. Click chemistry gave researchers the tools to build numerous desired molecules in just a few, straightforward steps, making the commonly used “Lego” metaphor of chemical synthesis real. Among all of the reactions fulfilling the requirements mentioned above, the Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of azides and alkynes stands out as it is the exemplar of a click reaction and has become the best bet for many applications. Specifically, this reaction has become a powerful strategy to reach many biomaterial science goals, such as efficient polymer functionalization for therapeutic purposes. Briefly, the commonly Cu-catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition is a chemical reaction between an organic azide (a 1,3-dipole) and an alkyne (a dipolarophile) to form and generate 1,2,3-triazole.¹⁵⁰ Huisgen dipolar cycloaddition can work in the water among a broad range of solvents and temperatures (0°C–160°C), possesses regio-specificity since it only yields 1,4-substituted products, and is a reaction on which simple purification steps can be carried out, such as dialysis or filtration.¹⁵⁰ Moreover, azides and alkynes are readily available, feasible to be chemically introduced, and remarkably stable in the presence of common organic synthesis conditions and in physiological microenvironments involving reducing conditions or potential hydrolysis.¹⁵¹

Several approaches have harnessed the other advantages of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to obtain protein and DNA bioconjugation,¹⁵² cell surface labeling, drug delivery systems (DDSs) labeling, and functionalization and chemical modification of biopolymer backbones.¹⁵³ Even though this reaction usually requires a transition metal ion catalysis (Cu⁺) to initiate it, the use of activated alkyne groups has been introduced to avoid some reported cytotoxicity issues. An ideal candidate for this particular purpose is cyclooctyne, and by using it in this way, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition can be performed catalyst-free.¹⁵⁴

Focusing on the topic of this review, it is worth highlighting how catalyst-free Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition (known as strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition [SPAAC]) has been used to cross-link ELRs bearing azide and cyclooctyne

functional groups, respectively, to fabricate hydrogels for several biomedical applications. The same approach can be used not only to cross-link polymer backbones but also to covalently attach epitopes of interest such as polysaccharides and glycan-binding proteins, with the only prerequisite for the couple polymer/epitope being to bear the functional groups able to undergo 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition. In the case of polymer backbones bearing side chains of lysines, it is possible to take advantage of the terminal primary amino groups to perform the appropriate modification. For instance, azide-functionalized ELR has been obtained in the past, applying the relatively mild and easy-to-perform diazo transfer reaction to amines introducing azide groups directly at the lysine positions. Cyclooctyne-functionalized ELR has been synthesized, substituting amines from the polymer backbone by (1R,8S,9S)-bicyclo [6.1.0]non-4-yn-9-ylmethyl *N*-succinimidyl carbonate coupling.¹⁵⁵ Virtually the same approach can be used to introduce clickable groups into several ECM-like polymer backbones of interest to exploit 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition subsequently.

One last relevant chemical reaction related to the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition-based glyco-conjugation strategy involves the feasible synthesis of glycosyl azides. In 2009, Noguchi et al.¹⁵⁶ reported the direct synthesis of glycosyl azides from reducing sugars in water. Some years later, this first route was improved to avoid the significant excess of azide, proposing that 2-azido-1,3-dimethylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate (ADMP) serve as an activating agent for the anomeric hydroxy group of the reducing sugar and at the same time as the source of azide. In this way, glycosyl azide can be yielded very efficiently, overcoming the oxazoline formation with a simple procedure.¹⁵⁷ Having the possibility of synthesizing glycosyl azide through this Shoda chemistry-inspired approach allows a subsequent, direct protecting group-free conjugation of sugar epitopes in aqueous media to any backbone containing alkyne groups. Moreover, if the polymer backbone of interest contains activated alkyne groups such as cyclooctyne, a one-pot, protecting group-free, catalyst-free glyco-functionalization would take place.

Depending on the base polymer (natural or synthetic), the formulation (insoluble or soluble polymers), and the sources (animal or recombinant), the assessment of affordable protocols to obtain reproducible glycoconjugates at satisfactory yields requires some troubleshooting. Specifically, each polymer exhibits reactivity depending on their source and molecular weight and on the active biomolecules to be conjugated. In addition, the purification and the characterization steps need to be decided considering the specific features of each polymer and glycan.

Non-covalent formulation strategies: releasing active molecules

As discussed in the opening lines of this section, to produce a particular therapeutic effect with a proposed biomaterial intervention, ECM-like polymers can serve not only as the backbone to attach active epitopes covalently but also as the matrix or vehicle to physically accommodate and subsequently release active ingredients of interest. In many cases, the covalent bonding of the particular pharmaceutical active ingredient is not needed and may not be the right choice to meet the desired biotechnological and therapeutic goals. While for some applications the most exciting strategy involves covalent immobilization on the material of choice¹³⁴ to prevent diffusion and enzymatic degradation of the epitope of interest, in other approaches the needs are diametrically opposed, and rational design of a suitable DDS is vital.

Several disadvantages can be encountered when administering specific active molecules. They will be distributed in the organism according to their physical

properties such as solubility, partition coefficient, and charge, and therefore, they can reach a variety of sites where they are outside of their therapeutic range, where they are inactive, or where their action is unwanted or harmful and, thus, causes adverse side effects. To address these drawbacks, therapeutically effective and patient-compliant DDSs are required. When designing a polymer or (in the case of this particular review) ECM-like polymer-based DDSs, different strategies to physically accommodate drug molecules within polymer chains forming the system matrix must be screened to select the most suitable one rationally. Due to the absence of chemical bonds to link the therapeutic molecule into the polymer backbone of choice, the efficiency of a DDS depends on the physicochemical properties of the couple drug/polymer and the processing conditions. Specific attention to the hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity character of both components and molecular weight of the polymer of choice needs to be considered. It is worth noting that even though these DDS may be covalently cross-linked to be able to retain their structure, the biomolecules they carry are not covalently bonded to the protein backbones, which is discussed further below.

In the following section, the two most relevant kinds of DDSs obtained from ECM-like polymer processing are described (Figure 4): hydrogels and polymeric microparticles/nanoparticles.

Hydrogels

Hydrogels can be defined as three-dimensional (3D) polymer networks that can accommodate a large amount of water or biological fluids in its matrix. Especially when considering ECM-like polymer-based hydrogels, the polymers involved are usually hydrophilic; therefore, before processing them to form a hydrogel, they need to be dissolved in aqueous media. The most relevant strategy to fabricate hydrogels involves physical or chemical cross-linking of the polymer chains to form the aforementioned interconnected network.

Physical cross-linking usually includes electrostatic intermolecular forces, hydrogen bonding, and thermal induction, among others, and can be applied to formulate hydrogels that need long-term stability or specific tailorable properties (i.e., degradation rate, tunable mechanical properties). Alternatively, chemical cross-linking involving the generation of the polymer network through covalent bonding can be performed using reactions described in this section. However, click chemistry, amidation, and photopolymerization are the most commonly used over ECM-like polymer backbones.¹⁵⁸ The chemical modification of ECM-derived polymers permits formulations of neoglycosylated hydrogels with exposed specific mono-, oligo-, or polysaccharides.¹²

The development of hybrid glycopolymers is of interest to mimic both the structural and biochemical composition of the ECM. Several examples of glycoconjugates have been developed with this aim, using different chemoselective strategies for the correct exposition of the glycans involved. The pre-functionalization of single polymer chains allows the control of the glycosylation of the polymers of interest and to produce 3D glyco-biomaterials that can find application in the development of injectable glycan-based hydrogels with embedded cells for cell-based therapies.

Hydrogels are also ideal for accommodating active hydrophilic molecules such as glycans or proteins, with such molecules being entrapped within the interconnected polymer chains during the cross-linking step, to prevent denaturation or premature degradation by inwardly diffusing enzymes. The need to load or co-load

Figure 4. Most relevant strategies to engineer ECM-like polymers as systems to deliver active molecules that are non-covalently attached to them

Being most relevant ECM-like polymers hydrophilic in nature, cross-linking them in aqueous media allows for the fabrication of tunable and safe to locally (i.e., intracranially) implant hydrogels able to physically accommodate and subsequently release active ingredients of interest, for instance, glyco-modulatory hydrophilic molecules. Furthermore, confinement or template-based methods can be used to successfully fabricate micro- or nano-architectures able to meet other biotechnological goals—for instance, intravenous administration to (1) target glycomoieties that are present in the endothelial walls forming the blood vessels or in some blood cells (i.e., selectins associated with rolling and tethering of inflammatory cells) or (2) harness the disrupted BBB to access brain tissue in some CNS-related conditions.

hydrophobic therapeutic biomolecules in hydrophilic polymer matrices (when the rationale biomaterial design justifies it) has also been addressed with some valuable strategies such as layer-by-layer.¹⁵⁹ Because these biomaterials are remarkably tunable, it is possible to modulate critical features for their available application by changing the experimental parameters. For instance, the hydrogel biomechanical properties and biodegradation profile can be customized by varying the polymer concentration, molecular weight, and polymer:crosslinker ratio. Hydrogels are particularly good candidates for brain local administration since they can be fabricated to be *in situ* forming, and therefore injectable, and they can match human brain tissue stiffness, providing,^{9,160} in addition to therapeutics controlled release, structural support as a synergetic regenerative approach in some neuroinflammation-related conditions.¹⁶¹ One promising approach that is emerging, for instance, involves the direct intracerebral injection of *in situ*-forming ECM-like hydrogels into the porencephalic cyst (“stroke cavity”) resulting from ischemic stroke to provide structural support in a lesion devoid of ECM, and in this way, promote the endogenous brain repair mechanisms.¹⁶² In the case of SCI, it has been seen that a multitude of ECM-like polymer-based hydrogels (e.g., collagen, HA) have been used successfully to bridge the gap in the injury site and also to act as a reservoir for therapeutic molecules that are released in the lesion.¹⁶³

In this context, hydrogels are a suitable option for the controlled release of hydrophilic glyco-modulatory molecules that do not need to be covalently engrafted in the polymer backbone of choice, but whose therapeutic effect can be exerted through their release from the hydrogel polymer matrix in their free form. However, it is essential to note that pre-functionalized polymer backbones can be cross-linked, rendering covalently functionalized hydrogels,¹² or that covalently pre-functionalized polymer chains can be cross-linked to non-covalently load or adsorb another active molecule in the final attained hydrogel. In terms of biomaterial design, the versatility and possible combinations are infinite. Glycosylation enzymes can satisfy this precondition since their action involves conformational freedom to act suitably on their substrates.¹⁶⁴ Similarly, glycosylation enzyme inhibitors cannot be covalently conjugated to a polymer backbone since their entire chemical structure is needed to block the action of the enzyme. Considering non-covalent entrapment of therapeutics, the release rate of the molecule of interest will be governed by the polymer matrix degradation mechanism and by the diffusion of the active molecule through water-filled micropores, forming the hydrogel mesh, which is another tunable feature. In general terms, by increasing polymer concentration, molecular weight, or cross-linker amount up to a stoichiometric ratio, it is possible to achieve a more compact microstructure, more effective retention of the active molecules within the polymer matrix, and an extended biodegradation and release time frame. However, it is essential to reach a compromise among all of these variables to meet the biomaterial therapeutic intervention of interest.

Polymeric microparticles and nanoparticles

In 1976, Langer and Folkman¹⁶⁵ reported for the first time the sustained release of proteins and macromolecules assisted by polymers. Ever since, particle-based polymer delivery systems have become critical players in the drug delivery field, attracting the attention of researchers working mainly in diagnostics and therapeutics. Therefore, microparticles and nanoparticles have been extensively used in biomedical applications, and many of these microtechnology/nanotechnology-based systems have been clinically approved.

Polymer microparticles and nanoparticles can be enclosed in a group of miniaturized polymer systems to the micron (1–1,000 μm), sub-micron (100–1,000 nm), or nanometer (1–100 nm) scale. These microscaled/nanoscaled constructs present distinctive properties when compared with bulk materials of the same composition that can be harnessed towards a targeted therapeutic effect. Choosing from microparticles or nanoparticles—in other words, aiming for a particular size in terms of the delivery system—will depend on the administration route, the entity to administer (drugs, proteins, or cells), and the biomolecular target.

Polymer particulate systems can accommodate active pharmaceutical molecules within their matrix in a manner that differs depending on the fabrication process and, thus, their final architecture. Solid particles and capsules (or core-shell particles) can account for the most common architectures, and each of them will offer widely different drug release profiles. Therefore, the choice to be made for a particular therapeutic intervention is not trivial. Thus, the selected technique to fabricate microparticles/nanoparticles must render effective processing, which guarantees that the selected experimental conditions will allow control of the formation of the particulate structure, their dimensions, and, ergo, their properties.¹⁶⁶ Many hydrophobic polymer matrices formed by a single polymer or by a polymeric blend have been extremely useful to efficiently load both hydrophobic and hydrophilic therapeutic molecules by emulsion-based techniques. Naturally, previously approved

polyesters such as poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA), polylactic acid (PLA), or polycaprolactone (PCL) stand out due to their remarkable performance over the years. However, when it comes to ECM-like polymers to accommodate cells, their intrinsic water miscibility may pose a challenge when efficiently forming microparticles.

To fulfill the scope of the present review, it is necessary to consider (1) why microparticles or nanoparticles as active molecules delivery systems can be of use when targeting neuroinflammation with a biomaterial-based approach and (2) how these systems can be fabricated from bulk ECM-like polymers that are hydrophilic.

To answer the first point, there are two main potential scenarios that one needs to consider:

A stable, long-circulating active ingredient carrier is required to achieve the desired therapeutic effect. Often, many therapeutic biomolecules of interest suffer from a short physiological half-life, and, therefore, their delivery can be assisted by polymer particulate carriers. In this case and considering an intravenous administration, nanoparticles will usually overpower microparticles due to outstanding size-related stability in the systemic circulation. As widely reported since the inception of nanomedicine, targeting the brain tissue using nanoparticles can be particularly challenging due to the BBB. However, it is worth emphasizing that as it often occurs in biomaterials- and nanotechnology-based approaches, the adverse pathophysiological scenarios can represent a therapeutic window of action. Many inflammatory conditions such as stroke and MS involve associated BBB damage, making it accessible to drug nanocarriers and therefore allowing permeation and retention in the brain tissue.¹⁶⁷ Another reason to aim for intravenous administration may directly involve the location of the target tissue. An example in this context is the administration of sialyl Lewis^x (SLe^x)-aiming selectins blockade to promote an anti-neuroinflammatory response (studied for anti-metastatic effect).¹⁶⁸ To be able to block the overexpressed selectins (mainly E-selectin), thus exerting the proposed therapeutic effect, the tetrasaccharide structure needs to be administered intravenously since the E-selectin is present on endothelial cells on the surface of blood vessels.

A microparticle/nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel-based scaffold is required because a multimodal release of different therapeutics is needed, a slow-release profile of an active molecule is required, or the active ingredient cannot be trapped in the hydrogel matrix and needs to be either accommodated in a secondary matrix through solid particles or encapsulated in core-shell structures.¹⁶⁹

The most reliable methods to fabricate constructs from bulk ECM-like polymers to achieve maximum drug-loading efficiency are inverse emulsion, sacrificial template-based, or microfluidics. In each of these methods, hydrogels are allowed to form through appropriate cross-linking in some kind of confinement architecture. In the case of inverse emulsion or microfluidics, this confinement is given by microdroplets or nanodroplets. Particularly when carrying out template-based techniques, the polymer cross-linking to form the hydrogel constituting the material takes place in the surface of a particle template that is subsequently dissolved, rendering core-shell structures. This latter approach also allows the possibility of layer-by-layer strategies to combine more than one polymer when it is needed and justified.^{20,170} Moreover, a combination with a non-sacrificial hydrophobic polymeric core can be implemented when this is in response to a specific biophysical goal (e.g., co-delivery of hydrophobic and hydrophilic molecules). Brain-targeted polymeric nanocarriers in particular have been broadly studied over the last 2

decades.¹⁷¹ A considerable variety of already pre-clinically tested nanosystems addressing brain diseases has been thoroughly reviewed elsewhere,¹⁷² emphasizing the importance of these systems in targeting neuroinflammatory-related scenarios.

It is worth noting that, aside from non-covalent drug delivery approaches, it is entirely feasible to process already covalently modified polymer backbones (thus, bioactive polymers) using the techniques that have been used to fabricate active and rationally designed biomaterials, which allow for the delivery of a plethora of glyco-active biomolecules.

Glyco-engineered biomaterials

As previously mentioned, collagen, laminin, and FN are naturally post-translationally glycosylated.^{173,174} However, the influence of the glycosylation of ECM proteins is still underexplored due to its complexity and dynamic nature, and because of the physical and biomolecular features of ECM components. Glycan diversity in terms of structures and roles highlights the significant effect of glycans from the ECM on cell fate regulation and tissue physiology. This is due not only to the interaction of ECM with cells but also the interplay between the glycans presented by the ECM with glycan-binding proteins and the presence of other proteins in the ECM and on the cell surface. The ability to modulate ECM protein function and structure through the conjugation of glycans or glycan-binding proteins is of interest for the enhancement of their natural glycosylation characteristics and for the formulation of new features. This way, the intrinsic properties of the polymers can be tailored to address specific dysregulated targets in a pathological condition, without requiring the use of living organisms. These glyco-functionalized materials can then interact with the cellular microenvironment and potentially remodel it.⁸⁶ This is an emerging field within glycobiology, glycochemistry, and biomaterials science, which is now starting to gain visibility. In this section, we focus on describing the glyco-engineered biomaterials thus far reported (applied not only in the context of the nervous system but also in other systems, such as musculoskeletal or cardiovascular), which underline the possibility of tuning ECM-based proteins toward different applications (highlighted in [Table 2](#) and [Figure 5](#)). Since the glyco-code present in the surrounding matrix can dictate distinct cell fates and regulate different functions in the tissue, the glyco-functionalization of proteins already described encourages similar approaches to be exploited to tackle neuroinflammation, using the diverse modalities mentioned in the previous sections.

The essential ECM protein used so far in glycoengineering approaches was collagen, particularly type I. Due to its ubiquitous expression in organs and tissues and its biochemical and mechanical properties, collagen is an attractive candidate for use in different applications. Therefore, collagen has been conjugated both with glycomimetics and with glycan epitopes. Masand et al.¹⁷⁵ reported for the first time in 2012 the functionalization of collagen with distinct glycomimetics. In this case, the mimetics of human natural killer cells (HNK-1) and PSA were used and attached to collagen through carbodiimide chemistry. These hydrogels were formulated and tested in neuronal cultures. It was seen that HNK-1-grafted collagen hydrogels enhanced motor neuron outgrowth, whereas PSA-grafted hydrogels encouraged sensory neuron outgrowth and promoted Schwann cell proliferation.¹⁷⁵ This work highlights the efficiency not only of glycomimetics but also of the conservation of their action when glyco-functional groups are attached to a polymer backbone. Collagen has also been functionalized with disaccharide sequences through reductive amination in both films^{13,145,179} and hydrogels¹² with di- and oligosaccharides to study the effect of simple glycans such as glucose and galactose, or oligosaccharides such as 6'-sialyl lactose and 3'-sialyl lactose or CS oligosaccharides.¹⁸⁰

Table 2. Glyco-modulatory materials reported in the literature with ECM-like polymer backbones

Polymer backbone	Glycans/ glycomimetics	Glyco-engineering method (chemical reaction)	Physical formulation	Methods used for characterization	Physiological relevance/ organ system	Application/main findings	Ref.
Collagen type I	Glycomimetics for HNK-1 and PSA	EDC reaction	3D (hydrogels)	stability (enzymatic degradation) <i>in vitro</i> response (ICC, neurite extension, Schwann cell proliferation)	peripheral nervous system (<i>in vitro</i>)	HNK-grafted collagen hydrogels encourage motor neuron outgrowth PSA-grafted collagen hydrogels promote sensory and motor neuron outgrowth and enhance Schwann cell proliferation and extension scrambled grafted peptides did not affect any of the cultures, unlike the native collagen first successful use of a glycomimetic functionalized biomaterial	Masand et al. ¹⁷⁵
Collagen type I	maltose (to expose glucose residues)	reductive amination	2D (films)	NMR, AFM, FTIR, ELLA <i>in vitro</i> analysis (cell identity, electrophysiology)	nervous system (<i>in vitro</i>)	electrophysiology experiments suggested that collagen matrices favored the expression of sodium and/or potassium channels in cell membranes, and this was more marked in the group in contact with neoglycosylated matrix neoglycosylated collagen matrix promoted F11 cell differentiation and proliferation (without the use of chemical differentiating agents)	Russo et al. ¹³
Collagen type I	lactose (to expose galactose residues); maltose (to expose glucose residues)	reductive amination	3D (hydrogels)	FTIR, anthrone assay, ninhydrin assay <i>in vitro</i> analysis (cytotoxicity, cell identity, cellular glyco-environment)	CNS (<i>in vitro</i>)	collagen conjugated with glucose: limited the astrocytic proliferation for up to 2 weeks and promoted the increase in sialylation while decreasing fucosylation expression glycan residues present in the matrix have a differential influence on cellular sugar expression the first example of neoglycosylation of collagen-based 3D structures	Rebelo et al. ¹²

(Continued on next page)

Table 2. Continued

Polymer backbone	Glycans/ glycomimetics	Glyco-engineering method (chemical reaction)	Physical formulation	Methods used for characterization	Physiological relevance/ organ system	Application/main findings	Ref.
Collagen	glycomimetic (for PSA)	adsorption into the hydrogel	3D (hydrogel)	<i>in vitro</i> analysis (cytotoxicity, proteomic analysis) <i>in vivo</i> analysis (glycomimetic availability, bladder function analysis, behavioral analysis, histopathological analysis)	CNS (<i>in vitro/ in vivo</i>)	this glycomimetic modulated the expression of NCAM by astrocytes <i>in vitro</i> <i>in vivo</i> , it improved motor functions after SCI and decreased the reactivity of astrocytes the glycomimetic seems to affect the balance between permissive and inhibitory factors and/or their interaction	Marino et al. ¹²⁴
Collagen-thiol type I	allyl α -D-glucopyranoside / allyl β -D-galactopyranoside	photo-click reaction	2D (films)	SR-XPS, FTIR, and ELLA; <i>in vivo</i> response (walking track analysis)	musculo-skeletal system (<i>in vivo</i>)	this approach can be applied for the chemoselective tethering of multifunctional ligands to thiolated surfaces walking track analysis displayed a significantly higher score in the Coll-S-Glc and Coll-S-Gal groups than in a sham group or collagen alone, emphasizing that neoglycosylation of collagen is more effective in promoting functional motor recovery than pristine collagen additional future studies are needed to verify the extent of cartilage regeneration <i>in vivo</i> and on the characterization of the mechanism of action the first example of neoglycosylation of collagen-based matrices by a photo-induced bio-orthogonal thiolene reaction	Russo et al. ¹⁷⁶
Collagen type I	3'-sialyl lactose (to expose α 2-3 linked SA residues) 6'-sialyl lactose (to expose α 2-6 linked SA residues)	reductive amination	2D (films)	contact angle, AFM <i>in vitro</i> analysis (cell morphology, gene expression)	musculo-skeletal system (<i>in vitro</i>)	MSCs can distinguish between the 2 different collagen-functionalized films due to the distinct saccharide-dependent stimuli they provide sialoside epitopes with α 2-6 linkage promoted the expression of aggrecan (a marker of chondrogenesis)	Sgambato et al. ¹⁴⁵

(Continued on next page)

Table 2. Continued

Polymer backbone	Glycans/ glycomimetics	Glyco-engineering method (chemical reaction)	Physical formulation	Methods used for characterization	Physiological relevance/ organ system	Application/main findings	Ref.
Collagen	decorin (proteoglycan)	entrapped in hydrogels	3D (hydrogel)	<i>in vitro</i> analysis (vessel growth)	cardiovascular system (<i>in vitro</i>)	addition of decorin improved dimensional stability of collagen gels without compromising vascular growth decorin-loaded collagen constructs are an attractive option for <i>in vitro</i> model studies on the effects of compressive mechanical loading on 3D microvascular growth	Ruehle et al. ¹⁷⁷
Collagen/ laminin	glycomimetic (for PSA): 5-NOT	entrapped in hydrogels	3D (hydrogels)	<i>in vitro</i> analysis (cell identity, neurite outgrowth, fasciculation, apoptosis) <i>in vivo</i> analysis (behavioral assessment, proteomic analysis)	CNS (<i>in vitro/in vivo</i>)	collagen/laminin scaffolds loaded with 5-NOT promoted repair of cortical neurons from astrocyte-mediated glutamate excitotoxicity these also enhanced neurogenesis and branching in cerebellar neurons (<i>in vitro</i>), as well as functional gain of motor functions after SCI in mice (<i>in vivo</i>) loaded scaffolds upregulated the expression of neuronal markers and downregulated astroglial markers at the injury site	Kalotra et al. ¹⁷⁸
HA/fibrin	galectin 3 inhibitor (2-azidoethyl [3-O-(2-naphthyl)methyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl]-(1-4)-2-deoxy-2-(3-methoxybenzamido)-β-D-glucopyranoside)	entrapped in hydrogels	3D (hydrogel with nanocapsules)	gelation time, porosity and surface morphology, rheological properties <i>in vivo</i> analysis (knee swelling analysis, histopathological studies)	musculo-skeletal system (<i>in vivo</i>)	galectin 3 inhibitor in the final DDS had the most remarkable impact on the suppression of synovial inflammation in the preliminary <i>in vivo</i> acute knee synovitis rat model further studies and tests are needed to understand the inhibitor behavior and its impact on the course of inflammatory joint diseases <i>in vivo</i>	Storozhylova et al. ¹⁶⁹

AFM, atomic force microscopy; CNS, central nervous system; DDS, drug delivery system; ECM, extracellular matrix; EDC, 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride; ELLA, enzyme-linked lectin assay; FTIR, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy; HA, hyaluronic acid; HNK-1, human natural killer cells; ICC, immunocytochemistry; MSCs, mesenchymal stem cells; NCAM, neuronal cell adhesion molecule; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; 5-NOT, 5-nonyloxytryptamine; PSA, polysialic acid; SA, sialic acid; SCI, spinal cord injury; SR-XPS, synchrotron radiation-induced X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

Glycan-functionalized collagen was used in different biological scenarios. For instance, collagen functionalized with glucose was shown to favor the expression of sodium and/or potassium channels in neuronal cell membranes and to promote F11 cells (neuronal cell line) differentiation, proliferation, and transmission of electric signals.¹³ However, collagen functionalized with two different sialyl lactose disaccharides (meant to expose sialic acids linked through two different linkages— α 2-3 versus α 2-6) was reported to affect the differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). In this case, sialoside epitopes with α 2-6 linkage enhanced the expression of aggrecan (a marker of chondrogenesis), whereas epitopes with α 2-3 linkage promoted MSC differentiation toward an osteogenic fate.¹⁴⁵

Thiolated collagen films have been used to conjugate allyl glycosides (α -D-glucopyranoside and β -D-galactopyranoside) by photo-induced bio-orthogonal thiolene reaction and tested in an *in vivo* model of osteoarthritis. The functionalized films were shown to increase the walking track score of injured animals, promoting their functional recovery.¹⁷⁶ However, further studies are needed to examine the extent of cartilage regeneration and to understand the mechanism of action.

Besides being directly functionalized with active epitopes, collagen has also been used to deliver glycan-modulatory molecules through non-covalent approaches, by solely entrapping them in a 3D scaffold (i.e., hydrogel/constructs). For instance, collagen hydrogels have been used to deliver a PSA glycomimetic in SCI in a rodent model. These hydrogels were reported to improve the behavioral functions of the animal and decreased the reactivity of astrocytes, both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.¹²⁴ Collagen constructs have also been used to entrap decorin (a PG), which was not detrimental to the physicochemical properties of the hydrogels and did not compromise vascular expansion, underlining its potential to be used in *in vitro* studies on microvascular growth.¹⁷⁷

In addition, collagen has been combined with other ECM-like polymers to formulate DDSs. Kalotra et al.¹⁷⁸ have developed a composite of collagen and laminin to devise hydrogels to deliver another PSA glycomimetic for the treatment of SCI. These loaded scaffolds enhanced neurogenesis and branching in cerebellar neurons (*in vitro*), and promoted functional recovery after SCI in mice, downregulating astroglial markers at the injury site.¹⁷⁸ Besides the collagen/laminin combination, other polymeric mixtures have also been attempted. For instance, HA and fibrin have been used together to fabricate hydrogels that have been loaded with HA nanoparticles for the delivery of galectin 3 inhibitor *in vivo*. This combination had a significant impact on the inhibition of synovial inflammation in the acute knee synovitis rat model.¹⁶⁹ However, more studies are required to understand the impact of this inhibitor on the course of inflammatory joint disorders *in vivo*.

Future perspectives

Even though there has been a greater understanding of how proteomics and genomics contribute to different disease conditions and pathophysiological processes, the role of glycomics in modulating the onset and severity of these phenomena has

Figure 5. A resourceful toolbox has been generated in the field to date using polymer glycoengineering approaches

This includes collagen-exposing glucose residues synthesized through reductive amination with maltose (i), PR-21 (glycomimetic for PSA)-loaded collagen hydrogels (ii), collagen exposing α 2-3 linked sialic acid residues and α 2-6 linked sialic acid residues (iii), collagen-exposing galactose residues synthesized through reductive amination with lactose (iv), 5-NOT (glycomimetic for PSA)-loaded collagen/laminin hydrogel (v), neoglycosylated collagen obtained by thiolene reaction between allyl α -D-glucopyranoside and allyl β -D-galactopyranoside and thiolated collagen (vi), hyaluronic capsules as a secondary matrix of hyaluronic acid/fibrin hydrogel to modulate a galectin 3 inhibitor (vii), decorin-loaded collagen hydrogel (viii), collagen functionalized with glycomimetic of PSA, and an epitope first identified on human natural killer cells (HNK-1) (ix).

only recently become clear. The importance of glycans in the context of immunity is only coming into significance, mainly due to the published studies on the endogenous interactions between immune cells and glycan-binding proteins. The inherent complexity and sophistication of glycan structures and their biosynthesis processes are challenging and stimulating, but at the same time, crucial for various functions. Their synthesis and remodeling through the action of multiple glycosylation enzymes orchestrate the glycomic profile of each cell and each tissue, having a central role in maintaining homeostasis. The structural complexity and diversity of the glycome pose a formidable challenge for functional and analytical studies to isolate and characterize specific biological functions of individual glycans. However, increased interest has grown in this field, leading to advances in both glycochemistry and glycobiology areas, allowing for the investigation into several glyco-based and biomaterials-based strategies that address the molecular signature of different disorders.

The use of polysaccharides is promising in the field of regenerative medicine for the development of new scaffolds, since this information provides valuable glycomic input in the design. Therefore, the different techniques described herein (both covalent and non-covalent), along with the polymers and active ingredients highlighted in this review, constitute a versatile toolbox with which to tackle some of the glyco-dysregulations seen in neuroinflammatory scenarios. It is also worth noting that the available glycan-based libraries are continually expanding since genetic engineering methods can be used to create novel glycomimetics or glycoconjugate polymers.

The emergence of glycoengineering as a vibrant and multidisciplinary field opens avenues for a new class of therapeutic biomaterials able to modulate complex but fundamental physiological mechanisms that are not fully harnessed to date. This field of research is still in its infancy, and combined multidisciplinary approaches and concentrated efforts are essential for progress. For instance, control over multiple parameters must be taken into consideration when fabricating glyco-modulatory materials, such as orientation, the density of glycans, type of glycan immobilization, linker used, and chosen carrier. Thus, the generation of complex glyco-engineered materials with specific targets remains the next frontier.

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DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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